

聖若瑟大學
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SAINT JOSEPH

ARKIVO

An Information System for the Preservation of Networked Crypto Art

A Thesis
Presented to
The Academic Faculty

by
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In Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for the Degree of
PhD in Information Systems
in the Institute for Data Engineering and Science
University of Saint Joseph
Macau

January, 2025

Endorsement

I certify that this report is solely my work and that it has never been previously submitted to any other higher education institution for any academic award.

I, the supervisor, believe that this Thesis is ready for assessment and reaches the accepted standard for the degree of PhD in Information Systems.

Daniel Filipe G. Farinha

Prof. Gérald Vincent Estadieu

To Geraldina and Lara

Abstract

Art registered on a blockchain as non-fungible tokens (NFTs), also known as crypto art, has gained popularity in the digital art world because it enabled artists to create scarce editions of their work. This scarcity of a digital asset in turn bestows the artwork with economic value, which attracts collectors looking to invest in digital art. It thus allows for the emergence of a global market for digital art. Perhaps more interestingly from a cultural perspective, artists have also adopted the blockchain as an art medium. Similarly to net art in the 1990s, some forms of crypto art are native to the blockchain and cannot conceptually exist without it. Code-based crypto art, specifically networked artworks, can be conceptually interpreted as being self-aware and evolving. However, these artworks are highly susceptible to obsolescence and, from a conceptual and technological perspective, pose significant challenges for their long-term preservation. This study focused on understanding these challenges and on experimenting with various conservation techniques aimed at solving them. Following a Design Science Research methodology, this project produced a software artifact, **ARKIVO**, for automating the archival, storage, and documentation of some of these artworks. It also proposes a new paradigm for creating crypto art, which embraces mutability and evolution as its core principles.

Acknowledgements

This work would not have been possible without the assistance and support of a group of people whom I have had the privilege to cross paths with in my journey.

Firstly I would like to express my gratitude to Professor Gérald Estadiou who, both as my supervisor and as my colleague, has had the patience to hear my ramblings about cryptocurrencies and countless project ideas for the past 15 years. For all his support, encouragement and inspiration, a huge thank you!

I would also like to thank Professor Carlos Sena Caires and Professor Álvaro Barbosa for their leadership and vision in the Faculty of Arts and Humanities, and for creating a working environment where creativity and innovation can occur, an increasingly rare commodity within our geopolitical context.

A special thanks is reserved for my great friend, and colleague, Professor José Manuel Simões, who is a truly inspiring human being and for always helping bring out the best in me. O Captain, my Captain!

I also owe a great debt of gratitude to my colleagues in the Department of Media, Art and Technology, Professors Filipa Martins, and João Brochado for all their support and above all for their patience when dealing with my absence from the office during the times I needed space to focus on this work.

I would like to thank Professor Adérito Marcos for inviting me to share my work-in-progress in the 2023 edition of the USJ Doctoral Symposium and for his support during the restructuring of my PhD programme between faculties.

A great deal of gratitude to my colleague and friend Marco Leong, for all his valuable insights in the latest trends in technology, and for suggesting that I look

into AdonisJS as a development stack.

Thank you also to Anthony Ifeanyi Okorochoa, for all his support when dealing with my endless questions about the formalities of thesis submission, even during his annual leave!

I would like to extend my thanks to all my other colleagues at USJ, academic, administrative and support staff, who all contribute to making this institution a workplace that I truly cherish and am proud to belong to.

A special thanks to Regina Harsanyi, for pioneering the field of conservation of blockchain art, and for her invaluable insights and assistance.

A great deal of gratitude to the Teia core team, especially Zih0r for his untiring assistance whenever I had questions about IPFS and the Teia infrastructure.

Also thanks to my co-members of the hicathon's collab contract group (wg3.2), Ztepler (@ztepler9000), Steve Jones (@1x1_music), Mical Noelson (@micalnoelson), and Shaman (@shamanovitch) for all their amazing work.

I would like to thank all the artists who supported this work, by participating in interviews, or simply by providing encouraging feedback, namely Raphael de Courville (@sableraph), Javier Graciá Carpio (@jagracar), James Bloom (@crashblossom1), Mario Klingemann (@quasimondo), Kath O'Donnell (@aliak), Thomas Lin Pedersen (@thomasp85), Bjørn Staal (@nonfigurativ) and Yazid (@yazid).

Thank you also to Chainleft, for kindly sharing his taxonomy of on-chain runtime art, and marchingsquare for sharing his views on code-based OBJKT security.

I am grateful to my parents back in Portugal for always supporting me, and to my new family in Macau for welcoming me and making me feel at home.

Finally, I would like to thank my wife and my daughter for their patience, love and support during this journey. They gave me the strength that I needed to complete this work.

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List of Acronyms

API	application programming interface
AST	abstract syntax tree
CID	content identifier
CLI	command line interface
DAG	directed acyclic graph
DAO	decentralised autonomous organisation
dApp	decentralised application
DeFi	decentralised finance
DHT	distributed hash table
DSR	design science research
HEN	hic et nunc
HTTP	hypertext transfer protocol
ICO	initial coin offering
IPFS	interplanetary file system
IS	information systems
NFT	non-fungible token
OAIS	Open Archival Information System

P2P

peer-to-peer

RQDD

research question driven development

SVG

Scalable Vector Graphics

UI

user interface

UTXO

unspent transaction output

UX

user experience

VPS

virtual private server

Chapter 1

Introduction

Blockchains have enabled a new global market for digital art, allowing artists to publish and sell their work directly to collectors from all over the world, bypassing traditional gatekeepers such as art galleries, auction houses and art dealers. Through chains of cryptographic proofs and consensus protocols which enable public append-only ledgers, blockchains can maintain the full history of an artwork's market transactions, from its inception (or minting) to its first sale on the primary market, and onwards through subsequent transactions on the secondary market, and thus natively solve, at least partially, the issue of art provenance, a long-standing problem in the traditional art world. In addition to that, with the use of smart contracts that automatically enforce artist royalties, artists can benefit from a life-long revenue stream, both from primary sales and secondary sales alike.

As is usual in the art world, when a new technology presents itself, some artists explore its possibilities as an art medium, and blockchain technology is no exception. Artists such as Kevin Abosch, Rhea Myers, Sarah Meyohas, and Sarah Friend, among others, pioneered conceptual art using blockchain as a medium, exploring new kinds of interaction between artists, artworks, and collectors (RCS, 2022).

Computational artworks with networking capabilities were made to interact

with their environment, and thus evolve. However, this network capability also brought with it problems. Many code-based artworks become immutable from the moment they are registered on a blockchain, yet the external environment with which they interact keeps changing, and often those changes are unforgiving for a code-based artefact which cannot mutate to accommodate them, in what can be called a *mutable dependency dilemma*.

This work explores that dilemma and examines the conservation of networked-based computational art through a technical and cultural lens of web3, which is native to the blockchain and crypto community.

This thesis contains many terms which were born out of the crypto community and may be unfamiliar to the reader. Even the term *crypto* itself, with its Greek origins, has been adopted by the cryptocurrency community, thus appropriating a term that until recently had been used mostly by the cryptography community. For this reason, this document contains an extensive glossary, starting from page 145, where many of the terms are defined.

1.1 Motivation

To better understand the motivation for this work, as well as contextualise some of the research and development decisions made during the study, it is helpful for the reader to review a brief timeline of the author's experience in the crypto space, which dates back to 2011.

Bitcoin

Bitcoin was announced in late 2008 (Nakamoto, 2008) and launched in 2009. The author first came in contact with it in the summer of 2011, when he installed the Bitcoin-Qt client software and received a small transaction from a public BTC faucet run by early Bitcoin developer Gavin Andersen (Lucas, 2022). On this occasion the user experience (UX) was underwhelming. The client interface was

rudimentary and the transaction took a significant amount of time to appear as confirmed. Compared to other online payment products available at the time, such as PayPal, Bitcoin seemed to be an inferior system. Such a superficial judgment of the merits of the technology is fairly common in the cryptocurrency space.

In 2013, upon revisiting the project and reading Nakamoto's white paper it became clear to the author that, despite Bitcoin's UX shortcomings, its overall system architecture presented a potential technological revolution in the way money is created and transacted. Instead of relying on central banks and commercial financial institutions to issue currency and maintain the ledgers of transactions, every individual could be an equal participant in a peer-to-peer network that completely replaces those centralised institutions. For the first time since money was invented, the ledger can be global, transparent and fully decentralised. Bitcoin therefore represented a new kind of global protocol for money with the potential to separate money and the state. At this time the author became an advocate, organising Bitcoin meetups in Macau (*Bitcoin Macau*, 2024), delivering public courses (Moura, 2021), giving interviews to the local media (TDM Portuguese News Programs, 2015) (Reis, 2017) and generally being very active in the Bitcoin community.

Ethereum

In January 2014, Ethereum was announced as a concept by Buterin (2014). Bitcoin always had basic scripting capabilities baked into its transaction processing logic (*Script - Bitcoin Wiki*, 2024), but to take what was mostly a transactional ledger technology and enhance it with a Turing-complete runtime was going to open a world of possibilities. Perhaps more importantly, Ethereum was also marketed as a decentralised platform where *code is law*, a concept which deeply resonated with the author. The idea of encoding governance into public, immutable, and self-enforceable rules seemed like a silver bullet against corruption.

In 2016, a bug was exploited in a smart contract of a DAO which held around

14% of all ETH in circulation (Morris, 2023). Under the *code is law* philosophy, the exploiter only followed the rules of the code and was, therefore, the rightful owner of the drained funds. However the Ethereum core developers dismissed the *code is law* mantra and proposed a hard fork of the blockchain (Buterin, 2016) to effectively reverse the attack, salvaging the funds from the hands of the hacker and returning it to their original owners. This was an extremely controversial decision, especially for a space where trustlessness, censorship resistance, and immutability of transactions are core elements. To make matters worse, in addition to such a significant u-turn in philosophy, how matters were dealt with, much of which was documented by an anonymous member of the community (yourstruly1, 2018), was very disappointing. Even if Ethereum Classic carried on with the original chain and philosophy (*Code Is Law*, 2022), the author was too disillusioned with the crypto space and took a step back from the ecosystem.

It should be noted that the author has since changed his stance regarding *code is law*, accepting that human consensus is key for determining what is economically valuable, as well as maintaining a sustainable long-term governance model. More important than strictly enforcing a rigid set of rules is to thoroughly document the intention behind those rules. This helps deal with unintended aspects of the rules, and informs future generations of the rationale behind those rules, whilst also providing the flexibility to adapt them to future realities that could not be predicted by their ancestors.

Tezos

In the summer of 2017, the author came across Tezos, a project still in its inception stage, but which was planning to build a self-amending blockchain with a well-designed governance system built into the protocol, giving its token holders voting power on updates to the protocol itself (Goodman, 2014).

This was exciting to the author because it promised to address the main problem that had led him to exit the Ethereum ecosystem. In addition to that, it

would also use a proof-of-stake consensus algorithm from day one, resulting in a much more energy-efficient and ecologically friendly blockchain.

Ironically, after delays due to extensive governance issues and disputes between the project co-founders and the president of the Tezos Foundation, who eventually stepped down (Irrera & Neghaiwi, 2017), Tezos finally launched in September 2018 (Dale, 2018). The delay in the launch is sometimes referred to as a reason why Tezos fell behind other projects in the crypto space, both in terms of developer mindshare as well as overall relevance, in what is a very competitive market.

The following three years saw a modest amount of development around Tezos, especially in the areas of decentralised finance (DeFi) and gaming, however adoption of the chain remained relatively low, as measured by the low transaction volume recorded on the chain, encouraging detractors to classify it as a *ghost chain*, as an analogy to a ghost town. In March 2021 all that was about to change.

Hic Et Nunc (HEN)

Hic et Nunc (HEN) was an NFT marketplace developed by Brazilian developer Rafael Silva, a former social scientist from Brasília. Lima launched HEN on the Tezos blockchain in March 2021, becoming the first to do so on that chain, and in the process beating rival marketplace Kalamint, which was still in closed beta.

At a time when the NFT market was experiencing a boom cycle (Hayward, 2021), many artists, especially those from the Global South, were priced out of the fast-increasing gas prices on Ethereum, on account of the high demand for block space. At the same time, environmentally conscious artists raised concerns about Ethereum's high carbon footprint since at that time it still operated on a proof-of-work consensus algorithm (Lemerrier, 2021). With Tezos offering very low transaction costs, and also being environmentally friendly due to its proof-of-stake consensus algorithm, HEN's launch on Tezos provided a solution for these two groups of artists. Prominent artists like Joanie Lemerrier and Mario Klingemann quickly saw the potential of the platform and started promoting it amongst

their peers. With an iconic minimalistic and raw interface, the platform invoked an underground culture of experimental and avant-garde digital art. It also intentionally lacked any kind of artist signup process or similar kinds of gatekeeping. Anyone with as little as 0.5 XTZ (approximately USD 2.5 at the time) in a Tezos wallet could mint an artwork on HEN. After only a few weeks, HEN rose in popularity and became a boiling pot of creativity and experimentation (Evans, 2021).

Pioneering museum strategist, and curator Diane Drubay, reflecting on the HEN experiment, stated:

“In March 2021, if you were minting on *hic et nunc*, you had no choice but not to sleep anymore. It was hectic and so beautiful! The energy was thrilling and every day was a new adventure.” (Drubay, 2021)

By May 2021 HEN overtook OpenSea, the largest NFT marketplace in Ethereum, in number of active users (Nelson, 2022) (Evans, 2021). This sudden rise in usage can be observed in the number of transactions and smart contract calls on the Tezos blockchain which started climbing just after March 2021, see Figure 1.1.

Each NFT platform on Tezos adopts a token name for its NFTs, and Rafael Lima named the HEN tokens: OBJKT, which is not an acronym. The term OBJKT was later *adopted* by a rival marketplace, *objkt.bid*, which then became *objkt.com*, and which is today the largest NFT marketplace in the Tezos ecosystem.

Figure 1.1: Transactions per month on Tezos blockchain (Jul 2018 - Jul 2024). Source: <https://tzstats.com/>

Networked OBJKTs and “Self-Aware” Artworks

HEN supported the minting of OBJKTs using a variety of file formats, and one of those formats was SVG (mime-type `image/svg+xml`). The SVG file standard allows for the embedding of JavaScript code, which is executed when rendering the file on a web browser. On 14 Mar 2021, French artist Lionel Radisson minted the first OBJKT with embedded JavaScript, “The Magician” (makio135, 2021), and other artists quickly followed and started minting dynamic code-based artworks. Ricardo Cabello (a.k.a mrdoob), the creator of Three.js, minted the interactive game “Jumpy Dot” (mrdoob, 2021) which became the first in-browser interactive game minted as an NFT (Rusher, 2021).

Figure 1.2: “Jumpy Dot” by mrdoob

Soon afterwards, the first few OBJKTs that made network (HTTP) requests appeared. The first ones only loaded external webpages or even played with recursion by loading the HEN website itself, but then these were quickly followed by OBJKTs that made calls to public APIs.

It was at this stage that Mario Klingemann (a.k.a. quasimondo) minted a conceptual OBJKT, “Planned Obsolescence”, which makes an HTTP request to a blockchain indexer API, giving it access to a real-time list of collectors of that OBJKT. The piece started with a misty, dreamlike landscape painting as

a background, but each time a new collector bought the OBJKT, the artwork’s JavaScript code would retrieve the collector’s Tezos wallet address from the API, and display it on top of the landscape, increasingly obscuring it, see Figure 1.3.

Figure 1.3: Three renderings of “Planned Obsolescence” by Mario Klingemann (quasimondo)

This kickstarted a wave of self-referential, some would even call it “self-aware” artworks, which also have the property of evolving. Many of which will be reviewed later in this manuscript.

This concept of “self-awareness” of an artwork struck a chord with the author, who decided to study it in detail. It soon became clear that this kind of artwork faces several challenges, which are discussed in section 1.2.

HEN Discontinuation

For reasons which are outside of the scope of this thesis, but which are reported at length in online articles (Straeubig, 2024) (Siqueira, 2021) (Tezos, 2022) (Smith, 2022), on November 11 2021, only 9 months since its launch, Rafael Lima decided to discontinue HEN. Without warning, the webserver which served the website’s UI was taken down (`hicetnunc.xyz`), and the official Twitter account was changed to show the message “discontinued”, see Figure 1.4.

Fortunately, Lima had followed the Web3 ideals of decentralisation and trustlessness when he designed and built HEN. The source code of the website’s UI

Figure 1.4: ‘discontinued’ by Rafael Lima. Source: <https://t.ly/PtiOd>

was open source and hosted on GitHub, and the smart contracts that the platform relied on were still operational on the Tezos blockchain and did not contain any *kill switch*, therefore they formed a sort of public utility infrastructure beyond the reach of their creator. The artwork media assets were available on a public storage network (IPFS) and therefore were publicly accessible as well.

The community that had formed around HEN quickly entered into action and in only a few hours several clones of the UI were setup online, in what the community calls “mirrors”, allowing users to continue minting, and collecting OBJKTs just as they did before. Efforts were made to ensure the continuity of the media assets on IPFS, and this was also achieved successfully.

After some time, the community converged on a particular HEN mirror, and after requests from Lima to not use the name HEN, the community renamed it Teia (“web” in Portuguese, in a gesture of respect to the Brazilian roots of the original project). Thus the Teia community was formed and the new website domain was adopted: `teia.art`.

Today, Teia operates as a Decentralised Autonomous Organisation DAO, is legally established as a non-profit organisation, and continues to operate thanks to a team of volunteers.

For disclosure, the author is a member of the Teia core team, which consists of 19 community members who currently operate the platform and oversee the

treasury by means of voting on a multi-signature smart contract on Tezos. The roadmap is to migrate the governance to a much larger DAO structure, where thousands of users who currently hold TEIA governance tokens, which were distributed based on their usage of the platform and contributions to the project, can vote on proposals related to the project.

As a Teia team member, the author's focus is the preservation of code-base OBJKTs, which are called Interactive OBJKTs in the platform's terminology.

1.2 Challenges

The biggest challenge facing a networked artwork is a mismatch between the immutability of the NFT and the fast-changing nature of the environment in which it operates. This is not a problem for the vast majority of artworks, because they represent static assets, such as images, videos, or sound files. As long as their file formats are supported by modern web browsers then they should continue to work for a reasonable amount of time.

Code-based artworks, if they contain all the required software dependencies and assets, such that you can successfully render them on an off-line device, should in theory also last a reasonable amount of time, notwithstanding the need for emulation at a later stage.

However, an artwork that requires data from external sources runs several risks because the data source can:

- make changes to the data structure that it returns (for example, API version upgrades)
- phase out a particular set of resources
- change the URI path of its resources
- limit access to its resources
- stop functioning (for example, organisation out of business, or project abandoned)

Any of these events would pose a problem to a piece of software which cannot be modified to accommodate those changes. This mismatch between an immutable software artifact and an evolving environment in which it depends will be called the *mutable dependency dilemma*.

The long-term preservation of the digital assets required by the artworks is also problematic. As will be discussed in the following chapter, there are several approaches, each with pros and cons, however, this is an area of heated debate in crypto art.

An additional challenge is that these artworks often lack the required metadata to differentiate networked, from non-worked code-based artworks. This makes it difficult for a conservator to identify which artworks may need attention.

Finally, although not directly related to conservation, any code-based artwork carries a security risk to those who access it, due to software vulnerabilities as well as potentially malicious code.

1.3 Goals

To address the challenges outlined above, and from an information systems (IS) perspective, two main goals arise for this work:

- To design and implement a sustainable IS that can support the long-term preservation of networked crypto art
- To contribute to the body of knowledge in the area of networked crypto art conservation

The reason why sustainability is explicitly included as an objective is because it is a requirement to support *long-term* preservation, and even though there are many types of sustainability which should be considered, in this context the key factor is economic sustainability.

The first goal is one that requires unpacking into actionable and answerable research questions, whereas the second goal will be collaterally achieved from

treating the first.

1.4 Research Questions

The first question that must be addressed is one of scope. How many networked OBJKTs are there on the HEN smart contract? Currently, this is not known, because there is a single category, *Interactive OBJKTs* for all artworks with mime-type `application/x-directory`, and there is no information about whether or not they make external network calls. In addition to that, as already established in the introduction, we know that SVG OBJKTs (mime-type `image/svg+xml`) can also contain embedded scripts and thus can make network calls. So now we have 2 groups of OBJKTs but no idea how to identify the ones of interest to this study. For this reason, the first research question is:

- RQ1: Can we determine which code-based HEN OBJKTs are networked?

Then there is the issue of documenting what these network calls look like in terms of the data structures being transmitted between the OBJKT and their external environment, so that they can inform conservators when the need arises to perform conservation interventions. At the same time, if we document these network calls, then perhaps we can also examine the rendering of the OBJKT to capture its aesthetic evolution. This leads to research question 2:

- RQ2: Can we capture and document networked HEN OBJKTs aesthetic evolution?

Finally, we turn our attention to the sustainability aspect of our goal. There is a wide range of elements involved in the sustainability of digital archives (Vis, 2024), however as suggested in the introduction, the low-hanging fruit problem that we want to address first is that of economic sustainability. Even if the infrastructure costs of digital archives are normally thwarted by the human resources costs (*Costs of Digital Repositories* | *Royal Society*, n.d.), the assumption for this study is that, just like Teia, this project will rely on unpaid volunteer work. Therefore, two final

research questions can be asked:

- RQ3: What are the disk space requirements for storing all code-based HEN OBJKTs' media assets?
- RQ4: Can an online archive for HEN OBJKTs be economically self-sustainable?

RQ#	Research Question
RQ1	Can we determine which code-based HEN OBJKTs are networked?
RQ2	Can we capture and document networked HEN OBJKTs aesthetic evolution?
RQ3	What are the disk space requirements for storing all code-based HEN OBJKTs' media assets?
RQ4	Can an online archive for HEN OBJKTs be economically self-sustainable?

Table 1.1: Research Questions

1.5 Contributions

The principal contribution of this work is an open-source web-based software artifact, **ARKIVO**, which:

1. indexes all code-based OBJKTs minted on the HEN smart contract
2. classifies the artworks according to their properties
3. executes and snapshots network calls initiated by the artworks during their execution
4. takes screenshots of the artwork during execution
5. stores a copy of all artwork assets

The system is live, accessible at <https://arkivo.art> and its source code can be accessed from:

<https://github.com/seda-studio/arkivo>

Secondly, a physical device, intended to be run from home, that contributes to the storing of the artwork digital assets. This component is key for the decentral-

isation, and long term economic sustainability of the project.

In addition to these artifacts, this work makes the following contributions to the body of knowledge:

1. Taxonomy and classification of code-based crypto art
2. Identification of networked OBJKTs minted on the HEN smart-contract
3. Analysis of the total asset size, and rate of growth of all code-based OBJKTs minted on the HEN smart-contract
4. A set of best practices for artists who plan to create networked artworks

1.6 Definitions

Although a comprehensive glossary is included at the end of this thesis, see page 145, this section outlines the precise definitions and scope of some of the key terms used in this thesis.

crypto art - this refers to any artwork which is registered on a blockchain as an NFT, and which exists purely in digital format, without any physical components.

It should be noted that this last assumption is more a delimitation of the scope for this work rather than a universal definition of crypto art, some of which can indeed have physical components. It is important to clearly define this aspect of the work at the outset, as the conservation of physical artifacts requires a very different approach to digital-only artifacts.

code-based art - this refers to any artwork which is created with computer code and which requires a computer to execute it in real-time to render the artwork. The term *encoded* is also used in some of the literature. In the case of this study, it specifically refers to artworks that use web technologies (HTML, CSS, JavaScript, SVG, and others) which are rendered in real-time by the viewer's web browser.

It follows then that *code-based crypto art* refers to artworks based on computer code which are registered as NFTs on a blockchain.

networked art - a specific kind of code-based art which initiates network requests, normally via HTTP or HTTPS, to an external URL which is outside of its artifact directory (identified by a specific directory URL). Any network requests made for internal assets (which are relative and internal to the artifact's directory) are excluded from this definition.

This is an important distinction because any code-based artifact will normally make several HTTP requests to load local assets (fonts, css files, media files) but as long as these are stored within the artifact's own directory they should always be available to the artifact, therefore not posing a *mutable dependency dilemma*.

conservation - "Conservation encompasses all those actions taken toward the long-term preservation of cultural heritage. Activities include examination, documentation, treatment, and preventive care, supported by research and education." (*What Is Conservation*, n.d.)

Regina Harsanyi, a preventive conservator of time-based media who works extensively with blockchain-related artworks, during an interview for this study highlighted that the code of ethics followed by conservation professionals is also key to the definition of the term (American Institute for Conservation, n.d.).

The terms conservation and preservation are often used interchangeably in the digital art literature, and definitions are often contradictory. For the purpose of this study, the following definition is proposed:

preservation - the goal of ensuring that cultural heritage remains accessible to future generations.

In summary, whereas preservation is the goal, conservation deals with the

methods and techniques to achieve it.

artifact - “an object made by a human being, typically an item of cultural or historical interest” (*Oxford Advanced Learner’s Dictionary*, n.d.). However, it should be noted that this term is used extensively in this thesis in two distinct contexts:

1. the software system, **ARKIVO**, which was developed as part of this research and constitutes its main contribution;
2. the crypto artworks which are the subject of the conservation techniques which this research explored.

It is somewhat unfortunate that this name collision occurred for these two types of artifacts, however, both are used extensively in the Design Science Research literature, which was the methodology adopted for this study, as well as in the existing software systems that already deal with crypto artworks. It is hoped that, when reading the text, the reader will be able to determine the type based on its immediate context. It is also for this reason that the other common use of this term, as a kind of error or anomaly, was avoided.

1.7 Delimitation of Scope

The focus of this research is on the conservation of networked crypto art, however, the scope of the artifact created for the study is delimited to OBJKTs minted on the HEN smart contract on the Tezos blockchain, and thus the analysis, discussion and conclusion sections of the work will also be delimited to that scope.

Having said that, section 4.1 (Survey of Code-Based Crypto Art, page 62) will provide a broader view and review artworks that may fall outside this scope, in order to provide additional context to the area of crypto art. Namely, it will review artworks minted in other platforms and blockchains.

1.8 Relevance of Research

Although the scope of the research may seem narrow, the subject on which it focuses is of significant relevance to the cultural heritage of crypto art. HEN, even if short-lived, is widely acknowledged to represent one of the most important cultural events and social experiments that happened in the world of crypto art, not only because of the art but also for demonstrating the importance of web3 principles (RCS, 2023) (Bailey, 2021) (Drubay, 2021). In addition to this, networked crypto art is a type of art that artists pioneered on HEN and hence of the utmost importance to be preserved.

1.9 Structure of the Thesis

This chapter introduced the motivation for this study, identified the main challenges of networked crypto art and outlined the goals, research questions and contributions of the study, followed by definitions of key terms, as well as determining the scope of the study. The remainder of the thesis is structured as follows:

Chapter 2 reviews related work, including digital art conservation theory, existing archival standards and tools, and the technical architecture of existing HEN OBJKTs.

Chapter 3 describes the methodology used in this study, namely Design Science Research, as well as the methods and tools used as part of the research and development.

Chapter 4 presents a survey of representative code-based crypto artworks and proposes a tentative taxonomy for this type of art.

Chapter 5 provides a detailed account of the prototyping phases when developing the artifact.

Chapter 6 describes the systematic analysis and evaluation of the artifact. It also provides a discussion on the lessons learned during its development.

Chapter 7 summarises the main points of the thesis, provides a set of recommended best practices for creating code-based crypto art, and outlines ideas for future work.

Chapter 2

Related Work

This chapter reviews literature and existing work which is of relevance to this study. It is structured in 5 main sections:

1. Review of digital and net art conservation theory
2. Review of archival standards and systems
3. Review of blockchain, smart contracts and NFTs
4. Overview of the architecture of Teia and HEN OBJKTs
5. Outline of some of the main challenges faced by blockchain and code-based crypto art

The review follows a narrative approach, with the goal of understanding the contextual background in which this work is situated. However it should be noted that there was a delimitation in the selection of materials reviewed, as only those which were made available as open access were included. In addition to academic papers, a number of books were reviewed, in the areas of blockchain art, net art, digital art conservation and information systems. A number of web resources in the area of art conservation were also consulted.

Due to the novel area of networked crypto art, there is not a lot of existing academic literature published in this specific topic. For this reason, the research for this work relied primarily on the existing work of conservation of the Web, the extensive literature on digital art conservation in general, particularly that which

focused on code-based art and net art, and also on a review of actual code-based crypto artworks.

2.1 Digital and Net Art Conservation

Due to the lack of existing literature on the conservation of networked crypto art, a reasonably good starting point is the study of computer-based digital art, which dates back to the 1950s (Higgins et al., 2023), and where possible focusing on net art.

Net art is an art movement which started in the early 1990s and gained prominence in the middle of the decade, fuelled by the rise in popularity of the World Wide Web (Schreiber, 2001) (Corby, 2013). It uses the Internet as a medium and is usually highly interactive often invoking the participation of the viewer (Kholeif, 2023). Although there is no clear consensus on a definition of net art, this study will adopt the definition proposed by Rhizome on their Net Art Anthology: "art that acts on the network, or is acted on by it" (*What Is Net Art?*, 2017). This emphasis on the interaction between the art and the network was famously captured by MTAA in 1997, see Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Simple Net Art Diagram. Source: MTAA (*NET ART ANTHOLOGY*, 2016)

Net art shares many similarities with networked crypto art. In fact, if we try to set them apart, the main difference between a net artwork and a networked

crypto art artwork is that the later is registered on a blockchain, and as per our delimitation of scope, operates exclusively in the digital realm. Thus networked crypto art can be said to lay at the intersection of net art and crypto art. This allows us to draw the first part of our conceptual framework.

Figure 2.2: Networked crypto art is at the intersection of net art and crypto art

Net art belongs to a wider category of digital art, specifically born-digital art, which designates artworks created in a digital format from the outset, and which depends on the technology to operate (Innocenti, 2013).

2.1.1 Conservation

As defined in section 1.6 (Definitions, page 14), conservation consists of a number of activities taken toward achieving the long-term preservation of cultural heritage. There is a wide range of such activities, but after a systematic review of digital art conservation literature, the following emerged as the most common:

- Acquisition
- Archival Storage
- Access
- Emulation
- Migration
- Restoration
- Reconstruction
- Reinterpretation
- Documentation

The following sections will examine these activities in more detail.

2.1.2 Acquisition

Acquisition is the process that a cultural heritage institution takes to obtain an artifact for conservation. It is normally divided into 3 phases (Ahtila & Akie, 1998):

1. **Pre-acquisition:** a pre-assessment of the artifact, to find its condition and whether it can be exhibited sustainably. This assessment includes an estimation of the overall costs, which include acquisition, exhibition, and continuing costs. If the assessment is positive, then the terms for the negotiation of the acquisition contract are drafted;
2. **Acquisition:** the process of acquisition involves negotiation with the vendor or donor, verification that all agreed components were delivered, including preservation materials, and exchange contracts;
3. **Post-acquisition:** work is catalogued and documented, and a long term conservation plan is made, potentially informed by follow-up interviews with the artist.

In a digital context, acquisition is also commonly called *ingest*, see subsection 2.2.1.

2.1.3 Archival Storage

Cultural heritage institutions involved in conservation of digital art need to develop a robust archival storage strategy. Depending on the size of the institution they may choose to invest in on-site storage, normally in server rooms designed for that purpose, or outsource it to specialised storage or cloud vendors, and in many cases for the purposes of redundancy, both.

In this area, the National Digital Stewardship Alliance (NDSA) published authoritative guidelines for industry best practices, see Table 2.1

These guidelines include the practice of *file fixity*, which consists of the use

of checksums or file hashing, as discussed in subsection 2.3.1, to ensure a file is “fixed” or unchanged. It also encourages a well known practice in the archival community known as *Lots of Copies Keep Stuff Safe* (LOCKSS).

Institutions are also adopting storage information systems which comply with the OAIS standard. This standard is of special interest to this work, so it will be examined in more detail in subsection 2.2.1.

Functional Area	Level			
	Level 1 (Know your content)	Level 2 (Protect your content)	Level 3 (Monitor your content)	Level 4 (Sustain your content)
Storage	Have two complete copies in separate locations Document all storage media where content is stored Put content into stable storage	Have three complete copies with at least one copy in a separate geographic location Document storage and storage media indicating the resources and dependencies they require to function	Have at least one copy in a geographic location with a different disaster threat than the other copies Have at least one copy on a different storage media type Track the obsolescence of storage and media	Have at least three copies in geographic locations, each with a different disaster threat Maximize storage diversification to avoid single points of failure Have a plan and execute actions to address obsolescence of storage hardware, software, and media
Integrity	Verify integrity information if it has been provided with the content Generate integrity information if not provided with the content Virus check all content; isolate content for quarantine as needed	Verify integrity information when moving or copying content Use write-blockers when working with original media Back up integrity information and store copy in a separate location from the content	Verify integrity information of content at fixed intervals Document integrity information verification processes and outcomes Perform audit of integrity information on demand	Verify integrity information in response to specific events or activities Replace or repair corrupted content as necessary
Control	Determine the human and software agents that should be authorized to read, write, move, and delete content	Document the human and software agents authorized to read, write, move, and delete content and apply these	Maintain logs and identify the human and software agents that performed actions on content	Perform periodic review of actions/access logs
Metadata	Create inventory of content, also documenting current storage locations Backup inventory and store at least one copy separately from content	Store enough metadata to know what the content is (this might include some combination of administrative, technical, descriptive, preservation, and structural)	Determine what metadata standards to apply Find and fill gaps in your metadata to meet those standards	Record preservation actions associated with content and when those actions occur Implement metadata standards chosen
Content	Document file formats and other essential content characteristics including how and when these were identified	Verify file formats and other essential content characteristics Build relationships with content creators to encourage sustainable file choices	Monitor for obsolescence, and changes in technologies on which content is dependent	Perform migrations, normalizations, emulation, and similar activities that ensure content can be accessed

Table 2.1: NDSA Levels of Digital Preservation Matrix V2.0. Source: <https://osf.io/qd54c>

2.1.4 Access

The archive should provide a user interface, allowing users to browse and search its contents, and in applicable to request copies of materials. In some cases some degree of access control may need to be put in place, in which case the system should provide such a feature. (National Library of Australia, 2003)

2.1.5 Emulation

Emulation is the recreation of a particular system, either hardware or software, as software which runs in a virtualised environment within another system (Rothenberg, 2000). It is one of the most common methods of preserving digital systems which became obsolete over time.

It is widely used in a variety of contexts, from reviving old video games, such as arcade¹, ZX Spectrum², and many other obsolete systems³, as well as more recent web publishing proprietary systems like Adobe Flash⁴ and even obsolete calculators (Scott, 2023).

OldWeb.Today, which combines web-based emulation of obsolete browsers, like NCSA Mosaic and Netscape Navigator, with Archive.org’s Wayback Machine web snapshots, enables users to experience navigating the web as it was all the way back into the 1990s, see Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3: OldWeb.Today Browser Emulator. Source: <https://oldweb.today/>

One challenge of emulators is that, as any other software system, they may

¹<https://www.mamedev.org/>

²https://archive.org/details/softwarelibrary_zx_spectrum

³<https://archive.org/details/software>

⁴<https://ruffle.rs/>

have to be readapted to run on more modern hardware. This means that the work of creating and updating emulator software is likely to be an ongoing effort for the foreseeable future.

2.1.6 Migration

Migration of a digital artwork involves moving it from its original technological environment, to a more modern one. However it is often the case that this will result in some degradation of the artwork, due to incompatibilities between the two environments (Huber, 2013).

As an empirical example of this, we can use the ACID test v2, which was a web page created in 2005 by the Web Standards Project to test web browser compatibility with the standards for displaying HTML markup, PNG images, CSS 2.1 styling, and data URIs (*Acid2*, 2024).

If we access the test page⁵ with a modern browser, such as Google Chrome Version 127 (released in July 23rd, 2024) on a Mac OS 13.6 operating system (released in September 21, 2023), and compare it with the reference image⁶, we can see clearly that backwards compatibility with web standards that were in place less than 20 years ago is already decaying.

This is a reminder that following web standards today is no guarantee of the fidelity of renderings in the future.

2.1.7 Restoration

Restoration is an umbrella term used for a set of conservation practices ”undertaken to restore an object to known preceding states” (Dekker, 2018). In general these are meant to be as non-invasive as possible in order to maintain the artworks’ authenticity.

⁵<http://acid2.acidtests.org/#top>

⁶<http://acid2.acidtests.org/reference.html>

⁷Test paged accessed on Google Chrome Version 127 (released in July 23rd, 2024) on a Mac OS 13.6 operating system (released in September 21, 2023)

Figure 2.4: ACID v2 test with modern browser ⁷

2.1.8 Reconstruction

Reconstruction goes a step further than restoration, as it involves rebuilding parts of an artwork, usually based on extensive documentation provided by the artist, so as to maintain their original intent, although it can be argued that any reconstruction is always susceptible to some degree or reinterpretation (Huber, 2013).

2.1.9 Reinterpretation

Reinterpretation represents the most radical intervention in the integrity of an artwork, as it may need to be adapted to a new environment, with new parameters. It may sometimes present itself as the last resort to preserve the artwork and, just like reconstruction, ideally it should be done in consultation with the artists as to maintain its original intention (Serexhe, 2013).

2.1.10 Documentation

Documentation is arguably the most important conservation practice in digital art preservation, being mentioned in the vast majority of articles and books.

Depocas noted that “sometimes this documentation is the only evidence left of an artwork’s existence” (2013, p.145).

Several efforts have been initiated by digital art conservation community in an effort to standardise documentation practices.

2.1.10.1 Variable Media Network

The Variable Media Network is a project that provides a set of guidelines and taxonomies, and a questionnaire which can help guide conservators in documenting digital artworks (Depocas, Ippolito, Jones, & Daniel Langlois Foundation for Art, Science and Technology, 2003). For example, artworks can be classified as contained, installed, performed, interactive, reproduced, interchangeable, encoded (our definition of code-based), and networked. Their questionnaire allows the recording of elements such as: stakeholders (persons, institutions, studios), artworks (title, year, description), components (material, environment, interaction), package (contained, installed, performed, interactive), questions (about storage, emulation, migration, reinterpretation), and allows the linking of these elements. For example a stakeholder, like an artist, can be linked to several artworks (*Variable Media Network*, n.d.).

The project also implemented a questionnaire⁸ as an interactive web-based application, as illustrated in Figure 2.5.

2.1.10.2 DOCAM Documentation Model

The Research Alliance Documentation and Conservation of Media Arts Heritage (*DOCAM*, n.d.) produced cataloguing and conservation guides, as well as a set of documentation models for the conservation of media art. This model “offers a

⁸<https://variablemediaquestionnaire.net/>

The figure displays four overlapping windows from the Variable Media Network Questionnaire interface:

- Add Stakeholder:** Features a dropdown menu for 'Type' (set to 'person'), a text input for 'Name', and a text area for 'Notes'.
- Add Component:** Includes a text input for 'Name', a dropdown for 'Class' (set to 'source'), a 'Requires' section with checkboxes for 'source', 'material', 'environment', and 'interaction', a 'Packages and Questions' section with icons, a text input for 'Examples', and a text area for 'Notes'.
- Add Artwork:** Contains text inputs for 'Title', 'Year', and 'Description', a 'Creator' section with an icon, and a 'Components' section with several small icons.
- Add Question:** Has a text area for 'Question', a text area for 'Answer/s', a 'Strategy' dropdown (set to 'Choose one'), and a 'Fewer/More' section with icons.
- Add Package:** Includes a text input for 'Name', a text area for 'Description', and a 'Behavior Parts' dropdown (set to 'contained') with an icon.

Figure 2.5: Variable Media Network Questionnaire.
Source: <https://variablemediaquestionnaire.net/>

structural framework within which all the information pertaining to a work can be assembled, organized, and made accessible” (Depocas, 2013, p.151).

Their model structures the documentation across 4 main lifecycles of the artwork: creation, dissemination, research and custody. See Figure 2.6.

- **Creation:** definition of the concept, presentation method, and required elements its presentation;
- **Dissemination:** presentation and publicity strategies, including installation, presentation, deinstallation and criticism;
- **Research:** activities surrounding the study or critical analysis of a work;
- **Custody:** various facets of custodial responsibility, such as storage, cataloguing, conservation and preservation;

Figure 2.6: Lifecycle events of a work as per the DOCAM Documentation Model.

Source: <https://www.docam.ca/en/documentation-model.html>

2.2 Archival Standards and Systems

Digital preservation is not a problem specific to digital art, and several efforts have been made to create standards for the long-term archival of digital assets. The following sections discuss some of the most significant ones.

2.2.1 Open Archival Information System (OAIS)

The Open Archival Information System (OAIS), an ISO standard, is the standard reference model for the long term archiving of digital data, and is one of the most quoted archival standards in digital art preservation. Its model describes best practices across all stages of a digital asset's life cycle: ingest, archival storage, data management, and access (CCSDS, 2012). These stages were taken into account when developing the artifact for this project.

The model makes reference to 3 types of information packages:

- **Submission Information Package (SIP)**: this is the information sent from the producer to the archive
- **Archival Information Package (AIP)**: which is the information stored by the archive
- **Dissemination Information Package (DIP)**: which is the information sent to a user when requested

It also makes recommendations with regards to the metadata that should be attached to each digital asset:

- reference (identification) information
- provenance (including preservation history)
- context
- fixity (file checksums)
- representation (formatting, file structure)

Figure 2.7: OAIS High-Level Data Flow.
Adapted from: <https://public.ccsds.org/Pubs/650x0m2.pdf>

This model constitutes the gold standard for digital archives, and is quite applicable to an archive of crypto art such as the one developed by this project.

As mentioned above, at a very basic level **ARKIVO** already implements the high level data flows illustrated in Figure 2.7. However a great deal of work is still required to address aspects of the standard such as migration, interoperability and others.

2.2.2 Archivemática

Archivemática⁹ is a web-based digital archive that follows the OAIS standard and integrates with many other data repository systems. It is open source, well designed and reasonably well maintained. However it was not suitable as a base software stack for this project because it relies heavily on web2 style authentication (username and password) and therefore it does not suit the web3 culture that our artifact needs to cater for.

2.2.3 Rhizome ArtBase

The Rhizome ArtBase is an online archive of digital artworks which underwent a significant redesign in 2021 as part of Lozana Rossenova's PhD work (Mehandzhiyska, 2021). At the time of writing it hosts 2318 artworks, ranging from websites, moving images, net art, code-based artworks, and games.

Following are screenshots of the main landing page, and an artwork page.

⁹<https://www.archivemática.org/en/>

Figure 2.8: Screenshots of Rhizome ArtBase.

Source: <https://artbase.rhizome.org/>

Each artwork page contains a basic description, and additional metadata about the artwork. It also contains linked objects (normally to the artist’s own website), archival copies, or both.

It does not provide a traditional search function, but rather a more powerful query service based on the SPARQL query language, which in theory should allow for complex queries of its Linked Open Data (LOD) infrastructure. However at the time of writing this feature fails run, even the demo queries provided by the system.

Its minimalistic design, which places the artwork first, was a major inspiration for the artifact developed in this work.

2.2.4 Archive.org and Wayback Machine

Although not specific to art, archive.org undoubtedly constitutes one of the most important archives of web history. It currently hosts 212 PetaBytes worth of web page snapshots, digitised books, videos, audio, images and software (*Internet*

Archive: Petabox, n.d.)

Unfortunately, Wayback Machine fails to capture any artworks rendered on Teia’s OBJKT pages, due to Teia’s client-side and highly dynamic UI. According to the LOCKSS principle, this is unfortunate, as having another archival copy of the artworks would be advantageous. Although it’s possible to manually request snapshots of the IPFS asset itself, bypassing Teia’s UI, in practice it would make finding such an artwork very difficult, as most users would be looking for the snapshots of the Teia URLs.

2.2.5 WebRecorder and WARC files

The WebRecorder project develops a number of tools for the recording (archival), and replaying, of webpages, similarly to the snapshots taken by Wayback Machine. These tools range from browser extensions, to desktop applications, and even command line tools and software libraries.

Importantly, snapshots taken by the WebRecorder family of tools conform to the Web ARChive (WARC) file format, which has become a standard in the industry (“WARC File Format”, 2024).

Such a feature would be highly valuable for our artifact, however through experimentation it was found that, unlike their desktop tools, the software libraries currently lack the ability to fully capture a web page with all its assets. Instead they only capture a single HTTP request. Lacking this basic single-page crawling ability meant that integration of WARC snapshots will be postponed for future work.

2.3 Blockchain Technology, Smart Contracts and NFTs

2.3.1 Blockchain

The concept behind a blockchain is not new. It was first introduced by Stuart Haber and Scott Stornetta in 1991 in the *Journal of Cryptology* (Haber & Stornetta, 1991). The problem they were trying to solve was: how can we trust historical records when digital media is so easy to manipulate, and how can we do so without having to trust a central authority? Their solution relied on one-way hashing functions.

Figure 2.9: Examples of one-way hashing (here SHA1 was used). The same input always produces the same hash. Different inputs produce different hashes, even if the difference is just one character, or even one bit.

Haber and Stornetta’s solution involved combining the hash of a document into the data input for the next document hash, resulting in a recursive chain of hashes which had an important property: any change to any of the documents, no matter how small, would break the chain of hashes from that point onwards. By weekly publishing the latest hash of the chain, which they did in the “Notices” classified advertisements section of the *New York Times* (Whitaker, 2019), they effectively created the first time-stamped proofs of the immutability of those digital documents, and arguably the world’s first blockchain.

Figure 2.10: Illustration of a chain of hashes

2.3.2 Bitcoin

Satoshi Nakamoto (Nakamoto, 2008) adopted this concept of an immutable data chain and added the required components to turn it into a global decentralised ledger, where financial transactions can be recorded. These components were:

1. a peer-to-peer network of nodes running the same software, which validates all transactions added to the ledger
2. cryptographic signatures, so that transactions spending or transferring a particular asset are only accepted by the network when signed by the asset's owner
3. the ordering of transactions into blocks, which are linked together by their hashes
4. a lottery system that determines which node on the network is eligible to publish the next block
5. a proof-of-work system with self-adjusting difficulty so that on average only one node is able to win the lottery every 10 minutes. Also the proof-of-work required for altering old blocks becomes exponentially larger with each block added, as an attacker would need to produce more proof-of-work than the rest of the honest nodes combined
6. a fungible token, bitcoin, which is used to economically reward nodes who

successfully publish blocks and is the native asset traded on the ledger

7. in addition to block rewards, block producing nodes (miners) also receive fees paid by each transaction which was included in their block

Although the blockchain contains a full history of all transactions ever made since its inception, Bitcoin stores the current state of the ledger, in other words, the index of who owns what, in a set of unspent transaction outputs (UTXO). As the name suggests, this is the list of all transactions which have not yet been spent by their recipients.

With his invention, Bitcoin, Satoshi created the first decentralised cryptocurrency, which exhibits several key properties:

1. **Decentralisation:** a peer-to-peer network of nodes, operates without any central authority
2. **Censorship resistance:** transactions cannot be stopped or censored by any central authority
3. **Permissionless:** anyone with access to the Internet can download the software and participate on the network
4. **Immutability:** transactions added to the blockchain become immutable, as explained above
5. **Transparency:** all transactions on the ledger are public, and independently verifiable, removing the need for trust (trustless)

2.3.3 Ethereum

As mentioned in the Introduction, Ethereum built on the concept of a blockchain, but unlike Bitcoin it does not use a UTXO approach. Instead, it uses an account-based model as a representation of the state of the ledger. There are two types of accounts in Ethereum: Externally Owned Accounts (EOAs) which are controlled by a person's private key and are used to send and receive assets; and Contract Accounts which contain code that gets executed when it receives a transaction

from an EOA. The code is executed by the Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM) which makes changes to the persistent state storage, see Figure 2.11.

Figure 2.11: Diagram of Smart Contract

Just like in Bitcoin, transactions in Ethereum must pay a fee to the block producers, called gas fee. In the case of interactions with smart contracts, the gas is consumed during the execution of the code, with each instruction (opcode) costing a varying amount of gas corresponding to the computational complexity of that instruction. Any unused gas is returned back to the EOA. Gas is paid in Gwei, which is a denomination of Ether, Ethereum’s native cryptocurrency.

2.3.4 Fungible Tokens

In the context of a blockchain, a fungible token is any digital asset issued and controlled by a smart contract or native to a blockchain, constituted by a large number of interchangeable and divisible tokens, and to which economic value is normally attributed by its holders. Blockchain native tokens, such as bitcoin (BTC), ether (ETH), tez (XTZ) and others are normally fungible tokens (also known as *coins*).

Ethereum standards, like ERC-20, define common rules and protocols that smart contracts must adhere to in order to issue and control fungible tokens which are recognised and supported by different wallets and decentralised applications

(dApps) built on Ethereum (*ERC-20 Token Standard*, n.d.). In this case, a fungible token is essentially represented by the smart contract which defines it. This smart contract also handles all token transfers and acts as the ledger that tracks the ownership balances of each holder. This standardisation effort made the creation of new cryptocurrencies a trivial effort, which led to the initial coin offering (ICO) hype of 2017, with many projects raising funds by issuing their own fungible tokens on Ethereum (Cuffe, 2018).

2.3.5 Non-Fungible Tokens

The ERC-721 standard is used for the creation of unique and non-divisible NFTs, each with a unique identifier, such that they are not fungible as their ERC-20 counterparts. Due to the limited storage available on the blockchain, the ERC-721 standard is defined as part of its `ERC721Metadata` a `tokenURI` field which should point to an external location where the actual NFT metadata should be stored. In turn, this metadata should follow the ERC721 Metadata JSON Schema, and includes the name and description of the NFT, and another URI, this time to the actual NFT media asset (*ERC-721: Non-Fungible Token Standard*, n.d.).

```
1 {
2   "title": "Asset Metadata",
3   "type": "object",
4   "properties": {
5     "name": {
6       "type": "string",
7       "description": "Identifies the asset to which this NFT represents"
8     },
9     "description": {
10      "type": "string",
11      "description": "Describes the asset to which this NFT represents"
12    },
13    "image": {
14      "type": "string",
15      "description": "A URI pointing to a resource with mime type image/*
16      representing the asset to which this NFT represents. Consider
17      making any images at a width between 320 and 1080 pixels and
18      aspect ratio between 1.91:1 and 4:5 inclusive."
19    }
20  }
21 }
```

Listing 2.1: ERC721 Metadata JSON Schema

Even though some early NFT marketplaces stored their NFT metadata and assets in private servers, leading to a loss of the assets when they shutdown (Gallen,

2023), nowadays most marketplaces store these in decentralised file storage networks like IPFS and ArWeave, which are more resilient see subsection 2.3.6 (Off-Chain Storage, 39).

Figure 2.12: Components on an NFT on Ethereum

2.3.6 Off-Chain Storage

As mentioned above, in order to avoid single-points of failure while storing NFT assets off-chain, most NFTs use decentralised file storage solutions to store their assets. Several projects offer such solutions, but lately two projects have gained relevance in this area: interplanetary file system (IPFS) and ArWeave.

2.3.6.1 InterPlanetary File System

IPFS is a suite of protocols for organising and transferring data over a peer-to-peer (P2P) network, using content addressing rather than location addressing, such as domain names or IP addresses. Content addressing works by hashing the contents of the file, or smaller chunks (or blocks) when the file is big enough, see Figure 2.13. This hash is known in IPFS as a content identifier (CID). IPFS then uses these CIDs to organise the assets in a Merkle directed acyclic graph (DAG) allowing for efficient storage and retrieval. There are several reasons why files

are split into smaller chunks, including faster parallel downloading from multiple nodes, and improving the chances of finding identical chunks between different files, which allows for chunk deduplication and hence savings in terms of storage space. (Ju et al., 2022)

Figure 2.13: Generation Principle of CID in IPFS. Source: (Ju et al., 2022, p.3)

CIDs are mapped onto the nodes (peerIDs) which host them, using a distributed hash table (DHT). Through network gossiping the nodes can quickly find a peer which hosts a CID. Nodes also cache CIDs which are retrieved through them, temporarily increasing their availability on the network. However cached CIDs are eventually garbage collected. To ensure the long term availability of a file on the IPFS network, at least one node must *pin* that content, which is to say, it prevents its own garbage collector from removing it and advertises itself a host of that CID. Since a CID is a hash of the content it assures the immutability chain between the on-chain NFT record and its off-chain asset. For those who do not wish to run their own IPFS nodes in order to pin data, there are commercial services available which will do it for a fee, such as Pinata¹⁰, and Infura¹¹. There is also Filecoin¹², a blockchain project which offers a decentralised marketplace linking storage node providers with paying users. Another service which specialises in pinning NFT assets is ClubNFT¹³ which, for an annual fee, pins all the IPFS assets corresponding to the NFTs owned by each customer, as well as providing

NFT discovery tools.

2.3.6.2 ArWeave

ArWeave is an alternative to IPFS. It relies on a blockchain architecture to provide permanent storage but, unlike traditional blockchains which suffer from scalability issues in terms of storage, ArWeave nodes shard the data amongst themselves, rather than keeping a full copy of the data in each node. It also uses a similar content addressing strategy to IPFS and, unlike IPFS, it only requires a one-off payment for perpetual data storage (where perpetual is defined as at least the next 200 years) (Williams, Diordiiev, Berman, & Uemlianin, 2019).

2.3.7 On-Chain Storage

It should be noted that even though the majority of NFTs follow an off-chain strategy for asset storage, some NFT projects seek to host all their assets directly inside one or more smart contracts, in what is called on-chain storage. The rationale is that on-chain storage is the safest type of storage since both the NFT, its metadata and media assets are stored in the same medium, and over a distributed network of independent nodes. Even though in theory this argument has some merit, upon a closer inspection a couple of issues can be identified:

- Even if all the artwork's assets are stored on chain, the artwork still needs a method in which to be rendered, may it be an SVG rendering engine, or some other method of rendering the asset's binary or ASCII code stored in the smart contract. Currently there is no standard method of communicating or documenting this process, which means on-chain artworks often still rely on off-chain documentation, knowledge of how to render the artwork, or a custom web UI which automates this process. Either way, there is often a

¹⁰<https://www.pinata.cloud/>

¹¹<https://www.infura.io/>

¹²<https://filecoin.io/>

¹³<https://www.clubnft.com/>

dependency on some off-chain component.

- As more data is added to a blockchain it increases the storage costs for nodes, which can compromise the level of decentralisation of the network. For this reason many blockchains look for strategies to reduce the storage requirements, for example, by allowing classes of nodes to prune some parts of the data leaving only a much smaller subset of nodes as fully archival nodes. Since multipurpose blockchains are meant to cater to a wide variety of use cases, the argument against on-chain storage of NFT media is that it represents a tragedy of the commons problem (Hardin, 1968).

2.4 Teia and HEN OBJKT architecture

As explained in chapter 1, this study will focus on the preservation of code-based crypto art, minted as OBJKT NFTs on the HEN smart contract, which lives on the Tezos blockchain, and which was subsequently adopted by the Teia platform after HEN’s discontinuation.

Similarly to Ethereum’s ERC-20 and ERC-721 token standards, Tezos defines its own set of token standards which specify the expected protocol and behaviour of smart contracts created for token issuance and management. In the case of Tezos the FA2 standard, as specified in the Tezos Improvement Proposal TZIP-12, supports both fungible and non-fungible tokens (Mishura & Mondet, 2020) (OpenTezos, 2024), and was therefore adopted by all major NFT platforms on Tezos.

In order to understand the overall structure in which OBJKTs exist, we will examine the architecture of the Teia platform, which is illustrated in Figure 2.14.

Three main smart contracts are currently used:

- HEN Minter contract: `KT1Hkg5qeNhfwPKW4fXvq7HGZB9z2EnmCCA9`
- HEN FA2 Token (OBJKT): `KT1RJ6PbjHpwC3M5rw5s2Nbmefwbwbdxton`
- Teia Marketplace contract: `KT1PHubm9HtyQEJ4BBpMTVomq6mhbfNZ9z5w`

When an artist mints a new OBJKT, the following process takes place:

1. The artist fills in artwork details in the Teia UI (including title, description, tags, number of editions, and royalties)
2. Teia UI prepares the OBJKT metadata, and uploads it, along with the artwork's assets to IPFS, via Teia's own IPFS infrastructure
3. Teia UI prompts user to initiate the blockchain transaction, via their Tezos wallet
4. User's Tezos wallet calls `mint_OBJKT` endpoint on the HEN Minter smart contract, including the metadata IPFS CID created in step 2.
5. The HEN Minter smart contract verifies the call, and calls `mint` on the HEN OBJKT (FA2) smart contract, where the OBJKTs are actually stored

Figure 2.14: Teia and HEN OBJKT architecture

After a few moments, the transaction confirms on the blockchain and the indexers, TzKT and Teztok, will pick up the new mint, and index it. This then

allows the Teia UI to pick up the change and show the minted OBJKT to the artist. The artist will also see the OBJKT appear on their wallet, with the corresponding number of editions specified in step 1.

At this stage the artist can list the OBJKT for sale, by making a subsequent transaction, which effectively transfers some editions from their wallet to the Teia Marketplace, where they can be collected by others for the specified price. Optionally the artist may chose to list editions for sale in other marketplaces that also support the trading of FA2 tokens, such as objkt.com.

Once minted, an OBJKT's metadata becomes immutable. This means an OBJKT can only ever point at one CID and that cannot be changed, see Figure 2.15.

Figure 2.15: HEN OBJKT Structure

2.4.1 OBJKT metadata

An example OBJKT metadata is as follows:

```

1 {
2   "name": "This is not an evolving artwork",
3   "description": "This OBJKT is only for testing purposes.",
4   "tags": [
5     "evolving",

```

```

6   "seda"
7   ],
8   "symbol": "OBJKT",
9   "artifactUri": "ipfs://QmbbgnKF94WowkANGrzRhJ4kZZaCjt85qC6ikW1XaaayBW",
10  "displayUri": "ipfs://QmbbgnKF94WowkANGrzRhJ4kZZaCjt85qC6ikW1XaaayBW",
11  "thumbnailUri": "ipfs://Qmac5jhpxNukkGm561jQN79Csp24s997PF51wvHxLKS3mz",
12  "creators": [
13    "tz1dd2tmTJFRJh8ycLuZeMpKLquJYkMypu2Q"
14  ],
15  "formats": [
16    {
17      "mimeType": "image/png",
18      "fileSize": 1706829,
19      "fileName": "not-evolving.png",
20      "dimensions": {
21        "value": "1024x1024",
22        "unit": "px"
23      },
24      "uri": "ipfs://QmbbgnKF94WowkANGrzRhJ4kZZaCjt85qC6ikW1XaaayBW"
25    },
26    {
27      "mimeType": "image/png",
28      "fileSize": 256717,
29      "fileName": "thumbnail_not-evolving.png",
30      "dimensions": {
31        "value": "350x350",
32        "unit": "px"
33      },
34      "uri": "ipfs://Qmac5jhpxNukkGm561jQN79Csp24s997PF51wvHxLKS3mz"
35    }
36  ],
37  "decimals": 0,
38  "isBooleanAmount": false,
39  "shouldPreferSymbol": false,
40  "rights": "cc-by-nc-4.0",
41  "date": "2024-08-26T15:13:18.882Z",
42  "mintingTool": "https://teia.art/mint"
43 }

```

Listing 2.2: Example OBJKT Metadata

In addition to the main `artifactUri` attribute mentioned earlier, OBJKTs' metadata may also refer to other URIs, as per the TZIP-21 standard (Dechant, 2020). Note how static image assets contain information about their dimensions (automatically extracted from the images by the Teia UI during the minting), however this is not the case of code-based OBJKTs (mime-type `application/x-directory`), also called *Interactives* in HEN terminology, as can be seen in listing Listing 2.3:

```

1  [...]
2  "formats": [
3    {
4      "fileSize": 1700696,
5      "fileName": "evolving-genesis-mint.zip",
6      "mimeType": "application/x-directory",
7      "uri": "ipfs://bafybeicx7ctb5n6bvvalsdlnsphizsopzejzw5zeqpurzu3jpkipmvxsle"
8    },
9    {
10     "mimeType": "image/png",
11     "fileSize": 1703771,
12     "fileName": "cover-evolving-genesis-mint.png",
13     "dimensions": {
14       "value": "1024x1024",

```

```
15     "unit": "px"
16   },
17   "uri": "ipfs://QmSHcauxV81hGvF89HF7VNXSeLpCJo4oPVSX7Gobns6Yfm"
18   },
19   [...]
```

Listing 2.3: Excerpt from Code-Based OBJKT Metadata

This means we do not have the information about the native resolution of the code-based OBJKT at the time of minting, and this causes issues when rendering these artworks, as the size of the iframe cannot be adjusted accordingly. This is a known problem with code-based OBJKTs which will hopefully be addressed some time in the future, potentially by prompting the artist to supply that information during the minting.

2.4.2 Content-Security-Policy for Interactives

When minting a code-based (or Interactive) OBJKT via the HEN and now Teia UI, a Content-Security-Policy meta tag is injected into the OBJKT's `index.html` page. This is done by the Teia UI itself. The original intention being the restriction of network requests to a list of allowed domain names, for security purposes. However this security measure can be easily bypassed by anyone who mints an OBJKT by interacting directly with the smart contract, bypassing the Teia UI, or using a modified version of the Teia UI (which is open source).

```
1 <meta http-equiv="Content-Security-Policy" content="
2 upgrade-insecure-requests;
3 default-src
4   'none';
5 frame-src
6   'self';
7 child-src
8   'self';
9 script-src
10  'self'
11  'unsafe-inline'
12  'unsafe-eval'
13  blob:;
14 style-src
15  'self'
16  'unsafe-inline';
17 img-src
18  'self'
19  'unsafe-inline'
20 data:
21 blob:
22 https://ipfs.infura.io
23 https://cloudflare-ipfs.com/
24 https://ipfs.io/
25 https://gateway.pinata.cloud/;
26 font-src
```

```

27   'self'
28   https://ipfs.infura.io
29   https://cloudflare-ipfs.com/
30   https://fonts.googleapis.com/
31   https://ipfs.io/
32   https://gateway.pinata.cloud/;
33 connect-src
34   'self'
35   https://better-call.dev
36   https://*.better-call.dev
37   https://*.cryptonomic-infra.tech
38   https://cryptonomic-infra.tech
39   https://*.infura.io
40   https://infura.io
41 blob:
42 ws:
43 wss:
44 bootstrap.libp2p.io
45 preload.ipfs.io
46 https://api.etherscan.io
47 https://api.thegraph.com
48 https://*.tzkt.io
49 https://api.tzstats.com
50 https://*.wikidata.org
51 https://*.coinmarketcap.com
52 https://api.openweathermap.org
53 https://hicetnunc.xyz
54 https://*.hicetnunc.xyz;
55 manifest-src
56   'self';
57 base-uri
58   'self';
59 form-action
60   'none';
61 media-src
62   'self'
63   'unsafe-inline'
64 data:
65 blob:
66 https://ipfs.infura.io
67 https://cloudflare-ipfs.com/
68 https://ipfs.io/
69 https://gateway.pinata.cloud/;
70 prefetch-src
71   'self'
72 https://ipfs.infura.io
73 https://cloudflare-ipfs.com/
74 https://fonts.googleapis.com/
75 https://ipfs.io/
76 https://gateway.pinata.cloud/;
77 worker-src
78   'self'
79   'unsafe-inline'
80 blob; ">

```

Listing 2.4: Content-Security-Policy meta tag added to all Interactive OBJKTs

2.5 Main Challenges

The following sections will highlight some of the main challenges faced by blockchain technology, code-based crypto art, and the crypto art ecosystem in general.

2.5.1 Scalability

One of the main limitations of blockchains is that of scalability. In order to maintain a reasonable level of decentralisation, where regular users can run fully validating nodes, the blockchain size must be managed carefully. For this reason there is a very limited amount of block size available for transactions, which in turn limits the transaction throughput of the network. One must remember that adding more full nodes to a network does not improve network scalability if each node must store the same data and replicate the exact same computation as every other node, which is the case with most consensus and block validating nodes on a blockchain (Khan, Jung, & Hashmani, 2021).

To alleviate this problem several solutions have been devised, the most common of which is what is called Layer 2 scaling. These involve performing transactions and computations on a separate chain or layer (L2) which then settles on the base blockchain layer (L1) (Zhou, Huang, Zheng, & Bian, 2020).

2.5.2 Code Security

One aspect that current digital and net art conservation theory does not cover, but which is a major concern for code-based crypto art is that of security.

NFT marketplaces have a global reach. Anyone can publish a code-based artwork, which is essentially a web application, and have it accessed by hundreds or even thousands of users. To make matters worse, the majority of these NFT marketplace users are likely running crypto wallets on their devices which could be holding significant sums of cryptocurrency and NFTs. This makes NFT marketplaces a potential honey pot for malicious actors who will be looking for ways to *drain*, or steal, the assets from user wallets. Attacks can either be direct by minting a malicious NFT, or indirect by infecting an open source library which may be used as a dependency by honest NFT artists. This kind of backdoor attack has already happened in the crypto industry when a malicious actor took over the maintenance of a popular javascript NPM module which was used as a

dependency in the crypto wallet CoPay (Haworth, 2018).

This risk is one of the reasons why some marketplaces apply restrictions to networked artworks. For example, OBJKT.com applies a security warning by default, with an option to disable it.

Even though addressing the security aspect of crypto art may seem to fall outside the scope of conservation efforts, the fact is that if a conservation tool is already automatically downloading and running artworks in a sandbox in order to snapshot them and preserve their evolution, then it is logical that it should also serve a useful function in this regard.

The area of malware scanning is well established, and it normally involves comparing the target software against signatures of well known malware.

Strategies can involve code similarity checks (Ragkhitwetsagul, Krinke, & Clark, 2018) and particularly in JavaScript (Alfageh, Alhakami, Baz, Alanazi, & Alsubait, 2020) where an artwork's code can be compared against well known wallet code.

Other ongoing efforts and research into code security checking include early detection systems based on machine learning (Schütt, Kloft, Bikadorov, & Rieck, 2012), detection of malicious obfuscated JavaScript code (Likarish, Jung, & Jo, 2009) (Fass, Krawczyk, Backes, & Stock, 2018), and malicious code detection based on semantic analysis (Fang, Huang, Su, & Qiu, 2020).

Some of these methods can also aid in identifying potential outdated libraries which could contain vulnerabilities or even current libraries which were attacked by hackers, looking to add backdoors or other crypto exploiting code.

However, research into techniques of camouflaging malicious code in a benign abstract syntax tree (AST) (Fass, Backes, & Stock, 2019) shows how easily some of the security measures can be circumvented, and serves as a timely reminder that this security minded endeavour may always become a cat and mouse game.

2.5.3 Copyright Implications

There is a general consensus throughout crypto art that the act of collecting an NFT does not grant the collector any copyrights over the NFT's original artwork, which remain with the artist (Çağlayan Aksoy & Özkan Üner, 2021). However the practice of NFT marketplaces engaging in cross-listings, which means displaying the artwork for sale on platforms other than the one where the artist minted the work originally, is widespread. It's a practice that is not only accepted, but arguably even appreciated by artists, who gain a wider platform for displaying, and potentially selling, their artworks. This is something that would not normally happen with a museum or other traditional institutions, who always have to go through a step of acquisition of the artwork, along with conservation-specific contract signing, before displaying or applying conservation techniques to it.

For the design of our artifact, this means that merely displaying an artwork on an art conservation platform, by itself, should not constitute a problem. However if the platform engages in automatic classification and displays such metadata along with the artwork, it may raise issues, as the artist may not agree with a particular classification or intervention. This is an area which needs further attention in future work.

2.5.4 Economic Sustainability

A recurring issue in blockchain projects, is that there is not enough market activity to sustain their business models, resulting in as many as two-thirds of all projects not surviving past the three years of operation (Franjkovic, 2024). Much of this is due to macroeconomic factors, and market cycles which are outside the control of the crypto community.

However one could also argue that better structures of support can be put in place, so that those services on which one depends do not suddenly stop operating. To help address this issue, a concept proposed by the author is the Value Distribution Protocol (VDP) (*Hackcoin, Hong Kong's First Blockchain Hackathon*, 2015)

(Farinha, 2016).

(a) Example VDP Configuration File

(b) Example VDP File Linking

Figure 2.16: Example VDP Configuration Files.
Source: <https://github.com/ktorn/vdp>

Figure 2.17: Value Distribution Protocol Example.
Source: <https://github.com/ktorn/vdp>

The concept is based on the idea of splitting revenue amongst stakeholders, including a small donation to project dependencies which enabled that revenue to be generated in the first place. If each project subsequently does the same, a tree of dependencies emerges, where value can flow from the top, where economic transactions are taking place, down to every dependency, and down to individual contributors. The idea was originally proposed for funding key open-source

projects that the Internet infrastructure depends on, but which are often forgotten about, such as OpenSSL and GPG (Oberhaus, 2019).

This is relevant for this study since the main goal is to design and implement a sustainable artifact that can support the long-term preservation of networked crypto art.

In this context, some progress has been made within the Tezos ecosystem, with the introduction of a collab smart contract during HEN's hicathon (*Hicathon Docs | WG 3.2: Sales Improvement - Split Sales and Royalties*, 2021), a project in which the author participated, and which allows artists to not only to split royalties amongst collaborators, but also to make small donations to *beneficiaries* from their art sales royalties.

In theory, if ARKIVO is perceived by artists as providing a useful service to networked crypto art, then by donating a small percentage of the royalties from the sales of those networked artworks to the project, then it could become economically sustainable.

2.6 Conclusion

This chapter provided a review of theory of digital art conservation, and reviewed the main archival standards and systems. It also provided a brief technical introduction to blockchain and NFTs. It then explored the specific architecture of Teia and HEN OBJKTs, which is the focus of our work. The next chapter will describe the methodology used in this study.

Chapter 3

Methodology

This chapter will describe the methodological approach to answering our research questions. It starts by selecting an overall philosophical paradigm, which will frame our approach to the problem. Then it describes the main research approaches. It introduces the main research methodology, and the specific research methods employed in this research project.

3.1 Philosophical Paradigm

Pragmatism was adopted as the philosophical paradigm for this research. This choice was made based on two factors: the work is highly practical in nature and pragmatism focuses on the practical nature of things and how they bring value and; pragmatism stood out as the best fit for the research methodology which was best aligned with the needs of this work, and which will be discussed in section 3.3.

Theories are meant to explain a true account of reality, however our view of reality is subjective, so how can we know if a theory is true? March and Smith note that “natural science theories receive confirmatory support from the facts that bridges do not collapse, medical treatments cure diseases, people journey to the moon, and nuclear bombs explode”, and propose that “truth essentially is what works in practice” (1995, p.255).

3.2 Research Approaches

For the most part this study relies on an inductive approach. For example, when approaching RQ1, the system must automatically detect and classify which OBJKTs are networked. To test the validity of the solution, a sample of OBJKTs which were manually classified is compared with the output of the system, and if all the items are properly classified then we can generalise that the automatic classification works for all cases. A similar approach is applied to the other research questions.

3.3 Research Methodology

This study will follow a Design Science Research (DSR) methodology, which is a well established methodology in the field of IS, and one where "knowledge and understanding of a problem domain and its solution are achieved in the building and application of the designed artefact" (Hevner, March, Park, & Ram, 2004, p.75).

Hevner et al (2004) describe DSR as having a dual set of core values: relevance and rigor. On the relevance side, the business, or in our case the community, reveals the need for the artifact by expressing a set of needs. Whereas on the rigor side, the design and development of the artifact is informed by applicable knowledge from theories, frameworks and other elements of the knowledge base. See Figure 3.1.

In the context of the artifact being developed, three main roles of stakeholders are identified: artists, collectors and conservators.

Some of the conservation theory and lessons acquired in chapter 2 will feed into our design decisions as we build an artifact that is grounded on good practices and principles. More importantly, the iterative nature of DSR will be adapted to a pragmatic development strategy that places the research questions as the primary development focus.

Figure 3.1: Information Systems Research Framework. Source: (Hevner et al., 2004, p.80)

3.4 Research Methods

This project used a variety of research methods, both for the preliminary study of code-based artworks, which developed into a survey and taxonomy presented in chapter chapter 4, and also for the development of the artifact, and its evaluation, which are detailed in chapter 5 and chapter 6, respectively.

This study primarily follows a systematic collection and analysis of the data produced by the artifact, in order to validate the artifact's ability to classify and document the OBJKTs as well as to determine the infrastructure requirements and financial costs. An analysis of the rate of growth of the storage costs was also performed, with the use of the R statistics software.

In a secondary role, a qualitative strategy was also employed, with stakeholder interviews, to gather additional evidence of the accuracy of the artifact in classifying networked OBJKTs, and to receive feedback which may be useful for future iterations of the artifact.

Even though both methodologies are used, due to the lack of integration or triangulation between them, this study cannot be classified as having a mixed methodology (Turner, Cardinal, & Burton, 2017).

3.4.1 Research Question Driven Development

In order to address the research questions, a new iterative development method was conceived, inspired both in the agile development method (Shore & Warden, 2021) as well as in test-driven development (Beck, 2003) but simplified and focused on answering the research questions. We'll call this method Research Question Driven Development (RQDD).

This process involves the development of an information system, the main artifact, and the observation of that artifact in a real world scenario. Each iteration is designed to either answer a research question, or to bring the artifact closer to such an answer in developmental terms.

The iterative development method is illustrated in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2: Research Question Driven Development

For each research question the following steps were taken:

1. **Design:** a design of the system components required to address the question was formulated. Following the pragmatic philosophy and with a rapid speed of development cycles, this step was often a mental process, rather than formalised as a diagram;
2. **Build:** the design was implemented through coding
3. **Run:** the implemented components were ran against real world data
4. **Observe:** the behaviour of the system was observed

After each iteration, if the observation satisfied the research question, the design was formalised as a model so as to contribute to the knowledge base, a new research question was selected, and the iterative process would continue. If, on the other hand, the observation did not satisfy the research question, then the process would restart, either with a refining of the same design or with a new design approach.

A key aspect of this approach is that it is the research questions that drive the development plan, rather than a set of initial requirements gathered by the stakeholders. This is intentional and does not dismiss the needs of the stakeholders. Much the opposite. By focusing on the research questions and bringing the artifact closer to solving the main goals, this method will contribute back to the environment or context of the stakeholders at faster rate than if the development effort were to deal with a much wider and fragmented set of requirements. Once the artifact reaches a state where it can perform its core functions, then the methodology can incorporate evaluations and feedback by stakeholders who, after experiencing the artifact in action, will have a clearer understanding of its intended functions and will be in a position to provide more valuable feedback.

Another key benefit of research question driven development is that, in the context of an DSR research methodology, the answering of the research questions constitutes the evaluation and validation of the artifact.

Finally, this method aligns with the Pragmatism paradigm, which serves as

the theoretical foundation of this study.

3.4.2 Interviews with Stakeholders

Even though not directly related to the research questions, semi-structured interviews were undertaken with stakeholders in order to provide a formative evaluation of the artifact, with the goal of refining and improving it in the future. The findings from these interviews will inform future work on the artifact.

Three stakeholders were interviewed, two artists and a conservator, through voice calls on Discord and a Google Meet videocall. In addition, three other stakeholders, all members of the Teia core team, tested the artifact and answered an open answer evaluation form.

3.5 Reproducibility

In order to facilitate the reproducibility of the findings, ARKIVO's source code and data analysis source files, including the data exported from ARKIVO's artifacts database table was made available publicly:

- the source code of ARKIVO is available at:
`https://github.com/seda-studio/arkivo`
- the source code for the hardware pinning node is available at:
`https://github.com/seda-studio/arkivo-node`
- the data exported from ARKIVO's artifacts database table, and the R source file are available at:
`https://github.com/ktorn/phd-thesis/tree/main/data-analysis`

3.5.1 Journaling

During the research and development, journaling was employed as a research method, primarily using two tools:

1. Obsidian¹: a note taking desktop app, for text-based note taking. This app allows rich formatting of notes using Markdown, and the linking of documents together, similarly to a wiki. It was useful to be able to quickly copy/paste text excerpts, quotes, code snippets, and other bits of information which were useful to record for later use;
2. Goodnotes²: a note taking mobile app, for hand-written notes on a tablet device like an iPad. This was used as the primary idea brainstorming tool, but also to take notes whenever the work laptop was not readily available. It syncs with a companion desktop app, so the notes would also be available on the work laptop.

Below are samples of notes taken with these tools:

(a) Sample Journal Entry on Obsidian

(b) Sample Journal Entry in GoodNotes

Figure 3.3: Sample Journal Entries

3.5.2 Thesis Writing

This thesis was written using LaTeX, a free and open source software system for typesetting documents, which is widely popular in the communication and publication of scientific documents. The main reason for this choice was a concern

¹<https://obsidian.md/>

²<https://www.goodnotes.com/>

that Microsoft Word might struggle in terms of performance when dealing with an increasingly large document, with many images, and references. From this point of view this proved to be a wise decision, as the full thesis can be rendered to a PDF file in less than 10 seconds. However it also proved to be a double-edged sword. LaTeX is a complex system, with many commands and configuration options, some of which may have unexpected interactions with each other. Several times unexpected formatting errors occurred in one part of the document, whilst attempting to fix another part, because of these interactions. It needs to be noted that when dealing with these problems, ChatGPT was an invaluable tool. Most of the technical issues were resolved simply by copy/pasting the LaTeX document source code into a prompt and describing the issue that was happening in the rendered document. Invariably the LLM would identify the issue and suggest the correct LaTeX commands to solve it.

The editing was done in TeXShop, a free and open source visual editor for MacOS, and the document was structured as one main file, which contained the preamble and overall document structure, and then individual chapters were included as separate files. Frontmatter sections, such as the title, abstract, and acknowledgments, were also all separated into individual files. This allowed for easier browsing and scrolling of each section, however when searching for text across the whole document one must then rely on the rendered PDF.

For most diagrams Google Draw, which is a part of the Google Docs suite, was used. The reason for this is that it allowed for very fast diagram sketching, which can be exported as SVG files. Then these files can be imported into the LaTeX document and adjusted for size without any loss of quality.

Inkscape, another free and open source vector graphics tool, was used to extract vector-based diagrams from existing literature. For example, Figure 3.1 in page 55, is a vector based diagram which was exported from the original article PDF, using Inkscape. Care was taken to convert all text into vector paths, so as to scale properly in this document.

3.6 Conclusion

This chapter introduced the methodology used in this study, which follows a philosophy of pragmatism, and that is particularly suitable to Design Science Research (DSR). It also outlined the various research methods employed in the research, including the novel Research Question Driven Development (RQDD) method created for this study and which focuses the development of the artifact on the answering of the research questions. This method will be expanded upon in chapter 5 - Artifact Development, page 80.

Chapter 4

Survey and Taxonomy of Code-Based Crypto Art

This chapter presents a survey of representative code-based crypto artworks, and provides a taxonomy that is relevant to the preservation of this type of art. Whilst not an exhaustive survey, this exercise was important for this study, because it provides relevant and applicable knowledge that informs the development of the artifact, and thus contributes to the research rigor, as specified by the DSR methodology discussed in section 3.3.

4.1 Survey of Code-Based Crypto Art

Figure 4.1: Simple Blockchain Art Diagram, by Rhea Myers.
Source: <https://rhea.art/simple-blockchain-art-diagram/>

In the following section several code-based crypto artworks will be reviewed.

They were selected for their unique properties, with the goal of providing a representative sample of the types of artworks available and helping understand the challenges that they pose from a preservation point of view.

4.1.1 Configurable API Endpoints

Stevie Jones, a.k.a. 1x1¹, a multi-instrumentalist, producer and coder originally from Northern Ireland, produced some of the earliest music NFTs. He also pioneered the use of an interactive options menu on OBJKTs which allows the user to modify the IPFS endpoint domain name on the artwork's UI, hence dealing with the mutable dependency dilemma directly on the OBJKT. This was the case with one of his early albums minted as an OBJKT on HEN, *Fragments from The Cross, Vol. 3*, see Figure 4.2.

Interestingly this piece also makes a request to `api.better-call.dev`, an endpoint which is no longer available. Stevie explained, in a personal communication, that the request was to check if the viewer owned two previous editions of the series, in which case additional content would be unlocked. From a preservation perspective, the challenge with this piece is the fact that it is fully interactive, and it requires clicking on each track to initiate the respective network request. A single automated snapshot archive of this OBJKT will be highly incomplete, as it will be missing all the media.

¹<https://1x1-music.com/>

Figure 4.2: Fragments from The Cross, Vol. 3 by Jules Maxwell & Stevie Jones.
Source: <https://teia.art/objkt/83079>

4.1.2 Requests to Private Servers

Figure 4.3: a possible landscape by Joanie Lemerrier.
Source: <https://teia.art/objkt/33076>

In a groundbreaking conceptual piece within the context of HEN, Joanie

Lemercier², linked the act of collecting the piece with the drawing of a physical plotter landscape, which would be revealed within the OBJKT itself. Minted at a time when there were no restrictions on network request destinations, Lemercier uses requests to his own personal domain, <https://joanielemercier.com>, to load the assets for each print completed. Similarly to Stevie’s Fragments of a Cross, it only initiates these requests when a user interacts with the piece.

Since, according to Lemercier, this piece is now “completed”, one single full snapshot, including the recording/archival of each and every landscape would suffice. This is an important intervention as the assets in the private server are at much higher risk than assets stored in IPFS.

Figure 4.4: Becoming-body by Jessica Luz and Carlos de Oliveira Junior.
Source: <https://teia.art/objkt/168794>

4.1.3 Requests to Indexers

Several networked HEN OBJKTs made use of requests to indexers, to retrieve the list of collectors, amount spent on the artwork, and other blockchain or market related data. We already mentioned “Planned Obsolescence” by Mario Klingemann,

²<https://joanielemercier.com/>

see page 8.

“Becoming-body”, a collaboration between Brazilian artists Jessica Luz³ and Carlos de Oliveira Junior (a.k.a. @vamos⁴), was created within the TIBUM residency. The artwork contains a series of 36 animated GIFs, which will swap each time the artwork is collected, see Figure 4.4.

4.1.4 Requests to RPC nodes

Yazid⁵, an artist and technologist from Brunei, has authored several networked NFTs, both as OBJKTs on HEN as well as in other blockchains. In his piece “OBJKTs (Mondrian Edition)”, Yazid abandoned the dependency on indexers in favour of embedding the Taquito JS library, which enabled the piece to contact the RPC nodes directly. In addition to cycling through 2 RPC endpoints for extra resiliency, the RCP API is also more stable than indexer APIs. A testament to this resiliency is the fact that this OBJKT still works today. The OBJKT queries the blockchain every minute for the latest OBJKT ID minted, and represents it as a series of bars in a Mondrian style, each column representing a digit of the number. See Figure 4.5. This means the artwork evolves rather quickly, with the rendering changing each time another OBJKT gets minted, in real time.

London-based James Bloom⁶ (a.k.a. crashblossom) is another artist known for his blockchain-interactive artworks. Using a mixture of requests to configurable RPC endpoints and private infrastructure, James creates artworks that react in real-time to changes in the blockchain. Mass, a blockchain-interactive artwork minted on Ethereum, is particularly interesting because the artwork monitors every action its owners take on-chain, and uses that data to enact changes in the rendered 3D space, in what James calls a “mass surveillance machine”, see Figure 4.6.

Preserving these types of blockchain-interactive artworks requires the preserva-

³<https://linktr.ee/jessicaluz>

⁴<https://vamos.com.br/>

⁵https://linktr.ee/_yazid_

Figure 4.5: OBJKTs (Mondrian Edition) by Yazid.
Source: <https://arkivo.art/artifacts/HEN/200599>

tion of the blockchain on which they depend, or at least snapshots of the blockchain data at given points in time, allowing for the replaying of the network calls initiated by the artwork's code.

Figure 4.6: Mass #1 by James Bloom.
Source: <https://opensea.io/assets/ethereum/0x80faa45d6f6cbdafdeba2f9c4a0237f74e5d8d9c/1>

4.1.5 Custom Renderings Based on Ownership

Another common theme amongst code-based OBJKTs is the customisation of the rendering based on whether the viewer owns the artwork. The piece can tell the

⁶<https://crashblossom.co/>

Tezos wallet address of the viewer because, if the user is logged in to Teia, it passes their wallet address to piece via URL query parameters. The piece then can query the blockchain to determine if that address owns any editions of itself, or even of other OBJKTs.

Raphaël de Courville⁷ (a.k.a. sableraph), a French generative artist and creative coder based in Berlin, has experimented with this idea in two conceptual artworks. The first one, Adam, consults the blockchain (via the hidex indexer) and gathers how many editions of the artwork have been sold, data which it uses to start erasing itself gradually. However at the same time it also checks how many editions of the artwork the viewer owns, and modifies the rendering slightly for them. These changes are subtle, resulting in a slow evolution over time, see Figure 4.7.

Figure 4.7: Adam by Raphaël de Courville.
Source: <https://teia.art/objkt/230177>

⁷<https://linktr.ee/sableraph>

(a) Viewer does not own OBJKT

(b) Viewer owns 5 editions of OBJKT

Figure 4.8: Detail of Adam by Raphaël de Courville (sableraph).

Source: <https://teia.art/objkt/230177>

The second, a collaboration with Malaysian artist Mumu⁸, “Moon’s medication: Your meditation”, explores the relationships between 2 OBJKTs. Instead of changing itself based on the number of editions that the viewer has of this OBJKT, it checks how many editions the viewer collected of another OBJKT, “Moon’s medication - Day”, and starts adding coloured medication tabs, with the number of colours reflecting the number of editions the viewer owns: red, orange, yellow, green, blue and purple, see Figure 4.9.

⁸https://linktr.ee/mumu_thestan

(a) Viewer does not own Moon's medication - Day

(b) Viewer owns 3 editions of Moon's medication - Day

Figure 4.9: Moon's medication: Your meditation by Raphaël de Courville (sableraph) and Mumu.

Source: <https://teia.art/objkt/631387>

4.1.6 Time/System Clock Based Art

Figure 4.10: Detachment by Thomas Lin Pedersen.

Source: <https://thomaslinpedersen.art/work/detachment/>

Code-based artworks that evolve deterministically, based purely on the system clock, have a very interesting preservation property: their complete evolution, which in theory can span thousands of years, is entirely encapsulated and self-contained in the code. Since all you need to provide the artwork with is the

system time, you can in theory rewind or fast-forward hours, days, weeks, or centuries in an instant.

Thomas Lin Pedersen⁹, a software engineer and generative artist from Denmark, encapsulated this philosophical concept of time-based determinism in his piece, *Detachment*, see Figure 4.11. The artwork is in perpetual slow motion, and one that is deterministically tied to the current time. Another interesting property of this kind of artwork is that any two viewers who open the artwork at the same time, as long as their device clocks are synchronised, will visualise the exact same rendering, even across different timezones, as the artwork uses the Coordinated Universal Time (UTC) time zone.

One can theorise that time-based artworks are, in fact, networked. However, instead of initiating a network request to an external API, they simply consult the API locally, which in JavaScript is as simple as: `new Date()`. The computer system in turn keeps that “data source” (the system clock) up-to-date by using external time servers (NTP), which keep the computers and other devices synchronised across the world.

Having said that, as tempting as it is to classify time-based artworks as networked, the fact is that they have very different conservation needs from the other kind of networked artwork that we examined before.

4.1.7 Browser LocalStorage Interaction

Several code-based artworks interact with the Browser’s LocalStorage system, normally to persist configuration options. However Bjørn Staal¹⁰ (a.k.a. *nonfigurativ*), an artist, programmer, and researcher from Norway, adopted this LocalStorage as an art medium, and produced *Entangled*. This remarkable artwork consists of a collection of 512 editions, minted on Ethereum (256 editions) and Tezos (256 editions) through the *fxhash* platform. Each of the editions is randomly paired with another across the two blockchains, and when one of these pairs are opened

⁹<https://thomaslinpedersen.art/>

on the same browser instance (as small floating windows on the same web page) they interact with each other, using the LocalStorage as a way to coordinate their relative X,Y positions on the screen.

Figure 4.11: Entangled by Bjørn Staal.
Source: <https://www.fxhash.xyz/vertex/entangled>

4.1.8 Self-Contained Data

All code-based artworks are in a way, data-driven. However all of the artwork types presented above require interacting with an external system for gaining access to that data, even if indirectly as is the case of the time-based artwork.

Javier Graciá Carpio¹¹ (a.k.a. jagracar), an astronomer, researcher, and creative coder from Spain, created several data-driven artworks that package their data with the artwork’s assets, therefore reducing its dependency on external APIs. This does mean the artwork’s evolution is limited to the data available to it at the time of minting. The benefit is that it makes for a very resilient artwork, with very simple preservation requirements. One such example is “50461 users in hic et nunc” which draws from a wide range of market activity to represent connections between users of HEN, see Figure 4.12. It should be noted that this artwork is user-interactive, which does increase the complexity of preservation.

¹⁰<https://linktr.ee/nonfigurativ>

¹¹<https://jagracar.com/>

Figure 4.12: 50461 users in hic et nunc by Javier Graciá Carpio.
Source: <https://teia.art/objkt/427089>

4.1.9 Determinism

This section deals with whether artworks are deterministic in the way they are rendered or whether there is an element of randomness that even given all the same starting conditions, the artwork will look very different each time. This categorisation is important for conservation because a nondeterministic artwork will be difficult to monitor from a browser obsolescence point of view, especially when using image difference between consecutive snapshots of the artwork. In the case of a non-deterministic artwork, the snapshots will be so different that they become ineffective in detecting changes due to browser version upgrades or other changes in web specifications overtime. In this context, the challenge is to differentiate between a deterministic animated artwork, and a nondeterministic artwork. This challenge exists, because even if an artwork is deterministic, unless there is a way to snapshot the exact same frame across all the snapshots then any image difference comparisons will result in exaggerated differences. In this case we may need to employ more advanced animation frame comparison algorithms, such that the sequence of the animation can be compared across snapshots, and these may involve the recording of the animation, rather than just taking a single

snapshot in time. Of course, such a strategy has trade-offs, and in this particular case the trade-off would be a much larger snapshot file size, which will then impact on the overall economic sustainability of the archive.

An example of non-deterministic artwork is Entropic, by generative art coding group united(fx)¹². Each time the generative artwork is refreshed, a new random seed is used, resulting in a completely different output, see Figure 4.13.

Figure 4.13: Entropic by united(fx) - 3 Renderings.
Source: <https://teia.art/objkt/853589>

It should be noted that, determinism is also a reason why fxhash flags or moderates any networked NFT minted on their platform. For example, Australian artist Kath O’Donnell (a.k.a. aliak)¹³ saw her networked data-driven artwork “Data as Landscape” flagged for this reason, see Figure 4.14. Fortunately for this kind of art, platforms such as Teia do not apply such restrictions.

4.2 Tentative Taxonomy of Code-Based Crypto Art

When looking at the preservation of code-based crypto art, it is useful to be able to classify each artwork according to a taxonomy that informs conservators of the specific conservation methods that may be required at a later stage.

¹²<https://unitedfx.xy>

¹³<http://aliak.com/>

Figure 4.14: fxhash flagging of Data as Landscape by AliaK, 2022. Source: <https://www.fxhash.xyz/generative/13124>

There is a clear lack of such a taxonomy in academic literature. Members of the crypto community have started efforts to classify code-based crypto art, such as Chainleft, see Figure 4.15.

Chainleft kindly shared a more detailed description of each category by private message, which can be found in Appendix 2, page 160. This is a good starting point for developing a taxonomy, however this study requires more fine-grained categorisation for certain technical elements of an artwork.

For this study we will start by proposing that all code-based art is, fundamentally, data-driven. This may fall outside the traditional idea of data-driven art, which is more often linked with data visualisations. The fact is that no code may run without the use of data stored in variables, and these variables maintain the internal state of the artwork. The artwork's visual rendering is only possible by materialising this internal state into visual elements on the canvas. The question then is how that data originates and which interactions cause it to change in a way that justifies capturing it from a preservation perspective.

Figure 4.15: Onchain Runtime Art by @chainleft. Source: <https://x.com/ChainLeftist/status/1757802497626767455>

4.2.1 User Interaction

The most common kind of interaction is user interaction, through the canvas and the usual input devices. This interaction may cause the artwork to change significantly from an aesthetic perspective, but it's a private experience between the user and the artwork. It is also more than likely an ephemeral interaction, without long-lasting effects on the artwork's state. As soon as the user closes the page or browser, the changes to the artwork's state are gone, and next time the user opens the artwork, it is back to its original state. The only exception to this is if the artwork saves state on the browser's LocalStorage or IndexedDB, causing it to persist between browsing sessions. Even then, this interaction is personal to the user, and does not affect the state of the artwork for other users.

The implication of this for preservation is that the recording of a user-

Figure 4.16: Code-Based Art Interaction Channels

interactive artwork should be orchestrated to also capture some of those interactions. This is a complex task to automate.

4.2.2 Time Interaction

As mentioned above, time or system clock interaction is the easiest to capture, because all that conservator or capturing tool need are the original artwork's assets. Then it is just a matter of manipulating the time supplied to the artwork to capture the piece in its entirety.

4.2.3 Other In-Browser Interactions

Similarly to user interaction, other modes of interaction within the browser really depend on each case. An artwork might make use of LocalStorage for enabling the interaction of two distinct tokens, as Staal did with Entangled, and in such a case the recording and documenting of such an artwork in its entirety, would be fairly complex, with so many permutations to consider.

4.2.4 Network Interaction

This study is primarily concerned with network interaction of code-based crypto artwork, because it can constitute both a persistent and an evolving state of the artwork. If an artwork deterministically generates an output based on this external state, then it can be said that the network *is* a part of the artwork, and needs to be captured for preservation purposes as well.

I should be noted that if the data source is the blockchain then, due to its immutable history, the full evolution of the artwork may be reconstructed in a simulation, by *re-playing* the historical blockchain transactions and events required by the artwork.

However, other data sources that do not benefit for that immutable record, and of the highest concern. Fortunately, from a preservation perspective, during the survey of artworks none have been found that rely on public, non-blockchain related, APIs.

Taking all the major themes from the review of the related work, as well as the survey of code-based crypto art, the following taxonomy provides a good lens through which to analyse and classify code-based crypto art.

Code Based	Is the artwork code-based? Does it include scripts?	
Deterministic	Is the artwork deterministic, or does it produce a random output each time?	
Storage	On-Chain	Are the artwork's assets stored on-chain?
	Off-Chain	Are the artwork's assets stored off-chain? (IPFS / ArWeave)
User Interactive	Is the artwork user interactive? (keyboard, mouse, etc)	
Network Interactive	Indexers	Does the artwork interact with blockchain indexers?
	RCP Nodes	Does the artwork interact with blockchain RPC nodes?
	Private Servers	Does the artwork interact with private servers?
	Public APIs	Does the artwork interact with public APIs?
Time-Based	Does the artwork rely on system clock / time for its evolution?	

Figure 4.17: Proposed Crypto Art Taxonomy

It is unfeasible to automate the classification of crypto art for all these categories at this point in time, but as we will see in chapter 5, we can automate two of them: code-based, and network interactive.

4.3 Conclusion

This chapter provided a survey of representative code-based crypto artworks, each one exhibiting a unique aspect of code-based art which requires different approaches to preservation. The proposed taxonomy and the classification of such artworks is only the first step in approaching their preservation, but is an important step as it may enable the automatic application of conservation techniques across classes of artworks, for example, the regular snapshotting of network calls initiated by network-interactive artworks.

Chapter 5

Artifact Development

This chapter describes the development of the artifact, `ARKIVO.ART`, following the RQDD method introduced in chapter 3.

5.1 Plan Breakdown

To answer a research question, one starts to plan what is required to answer the question, and then works backwards in incremental stages to where we are currently, leaving milestones (Miles) along the way, starting at 1 and going upwards as we get away from the goal. The analogy is that of a road, with side-road markers, each showing how many miles away we are from our destination.

The decision of *how* to group the Miles into Iterations really depends on the complexity of each Mile, and their relationships and dependencies.

Finally, all Mile and Iteration labels should be prefixed with the RQ number that they correspond to, for example: `RQ1.Mile 5`, `RQ1.Iteration 1`. This ensures unique identifiers across a project. However due to space limitations in this document, only Iterations will show the prefix.

Figure 5.1 illustrates a model of this reverse-planning forward-execution method.

Figure 5.1: Mile and Iteration Planning Process

5.2 Plan for RQ1

We will start by trying to answer RQ1:

RQ1 - Can we determine which code-based HEN OBJKTs are networked?

We know that we can do this manually, by opening the OBJKT on a web browser and inspecting the network tab under the Developer Tools, to determine if there is any network activity to a domain or URL path that is outside of the OBJKT's IPFS URL. As an example we will use the artwork "Adam" by Raphaël de Courville¹, which we know to be a networked OBJKT. As seen in Figure 5.2, there is indeed a request to an external endpoint: `https://api.hicdex.com/v1/graphql` initiated by `sketch.js`, which is the p5js sketch that renders this artwork. The remaining 3 network requests are for local assets within the directory of the OBJKT, and hence not considered 'networking' as per our initial definition.

Now that we established that we can identify a networked OBJKT manually, the next step is to do it programmatically.

At this stage we can start to plan our Miles. The numbers will go up the

¹<https://cache.teia.rocks/ipfs/QmbNtTu7k2E2UDYDQTYiVzV8rVbCU44hc9js1erKzeSogY/?creator=tz1hfuVWgcJ89ZE75ut9Qroi3y7GFJL5Lf2K&viewer=&objkt=230177>

Figure 5.2: Developer Tools - Network Inspection

further we get away from our goal.

Analysing the network traffic and determining if an OBJKT is networked is Mile 1.

For capturing the network traffic programatically we can use one of several headless browser automation solutions, which are normally used for automated website testing and web-scraping, like Playwright², Selenium³, or Puppeteer⁴. For this work Playwright was selected. This is Mile 2.

Although our Playwright instance could access the OBJKT asset directly from the Teia IPFS node, there are several reasons why it's not desirable to do so:

1. introduces potential network latency which could affect the snapshot process adversely
2. increases the bandwidth usage between teia and arkivo
3. arkivo is supposed to archive these artworks anyway, including full copies of the assets

For this reason the next step is to run our own IPFS node, so that we can fetch the OBJKTs locally, and pin them, which ensured it cannot be garbage collected by the node. This is Mile 3.

But this raises another question, which artworks to fetch? We need a way to

²<https://playwright.dev/>

³<https://www.selenium.dev/>

⁴<https://pptr.dev/>

discover and index all the OBJKTs that we are interested in investigating. This is Mile 4.

To discover the OBJKTs we can resort to existing indexers of the Tezos blockchain. There are 2 main options:

1. TzKT API⁵ - a generic indexer for the whole Tezos blockchain
2. TezTok API⁶ - an indexer specialised in Tezos NFTs

The TzKT API being generic, operates at a very low level, with endpoints that are closely related to the blockchain data, without abstraction layers. TezTok, on the other hand, specialises in NFTs so it creates an abstraction layer that is easier to work with, since it is NFTs we are interested in discovering. For this reason TezTok was chosen.

Finally, we can move to the last stage, determining what search criteria to use when querying TezTok. This is Mile 5.

Below is a summary of the five Miles. We will write them in the reverse order, as now we are going back towards our goal, see Table 5.1.

Mile	Description
Mile 5	Determine search criteria to use in Mile 4
Mile 4	Query TezTok to identify which artworks to fetch (discovery)
Mile 3	Fetch and pin all OBJKTs of potential interest
Mile 2	Run OBJKT in Playwright sandbox and capture traffic
Mile 1	Analyse traffic and determine if the OBJKT is networked

Table 5.1: The 5 Miles of Development for RQ1

With these in place we draft an iteration plan. This can always be changed later but will give a rough idea of how many iterations are required, see Table 5.2.

Iteration	Mile	Description
Iteration RQ1.1	Mile 5	Determine search criteria to use in Mile 4
	Mile 4	Query TezTok to identify which artworks to fetch (discovery)
Iteration RQ1.2	Mile 3	Fetch and pin all OBJKTs of potential interest
Iteration RQ1.3	Mile 2	Run OBJKT in Playwright sandbox and capture traffic
	Mile 1	Analyse traffic and determine if the OBJKT is networked

Table 5.2: Iteration Plan for RQ1

⁵<https://tzkt.io/api>

⁶<https://www.teztok.com>

5.3 Iteration RQ1.1

In this section, the first iteration will be implemented, see Table 5.3.

Iteration	Mile	Description
Iteration RQ1.1	Mile 5	Determine search criteria to use in Mile 4
	Mile 4	Query TezTok to identify which artworks to fetch (discovery)

Table 5.3: Iteration RQ1.1 Miles

5.3.1 Mile 5 - Determine search criteria

Mile 5 is really just an exploratory phase, which does not require any development. It involves accessing TezTok's GraphQL playground⁷, exploring the schema available, and crafting a query that returns a list of OBJKTs of interest.

We want all OBJKTs of mime-type `application/x-directory` and `image/svg+xml` from the HEN OBJKT smart contract `KT1RJ6PbjHpwc3M5rw5s2Nbmefwbubdxton` and we select all the metadata fields that are interesting to us, including `artifact_uri` which is the CID of the OBJKT media asset in the IPFS network.

```

1 query artifact_metadata {
2   tokens(where: {_or: [{mime_type: {_eq: "application/x-directory"}},
3     {mime_type: {_eq: "image/svg+xml"}}]},
4     fa2_address: {_eq: "KT1RJ6PbjHpwc3M5rw5s2Nbmefwbubdxton"},
5     order_by: {minted_at: asc}, offset: 0, limit: 10) {
6     token_id
7     name
8     artifact_uri
9     metadata_uri
10    thumbnail_uri
11    mime_type
12    description
13    tags {
14      tag
15    }
16    artist_address
17    fa2_address
18    platform
19    minted_at
20    editions
21  }
22 }
```

Listing 5.1: GraphQL query to retrieve OBJKTs of interest

Following is a sample of a record returned by this query:

⁷<https://graphiql.teztok.com/>

```

1 "tokens": [
2   {
3     "token_id": "229",
4     "name": "The Bird",
5     "artifact_uri": "ipfs://QmUHJdbFukpVBSqVnQ7V1C9JEFR5XC2pFZW17LUEpAtQnd",
6     "metadata_uri": "ipfs://QmbaWzPvtJJXJT8bqxUrFUQkraV3uHV4rzzrXFLBcJ18kH1",
7     "thumbnail_uri": "ipfs://QmNrhZHUaEqxhyLfqq1mtHSipkWHeT31LNhb1QEbdHgnc",
8     "mime_type": "image/svg+xml",
9     "description": "The Bird. SVG. 2021. @djangobits",
10    "tags": [],
11    "artist_address": "tz1YRG68NdqtAcSFEwTUw6FsSsiBb5kagEDo",
12    "fa2_address": "KT1RJ6PbjHpwc3M5rw5s2Nbmefwbubdxt0n",
13    "platform": "HEN",
14    "minted_at": "2021-03-02T06:16:35+00:00",
15    "editions": 1
16  },
17  [snip]

```

Listing 5.2: Sample OBJKT Record

5.3.2 Mile 4 - Query TezTok

Mile 4 is the beginning of development, therefore at this stage we need to develop a barebones application. For this project the AdonisJS web framework was selected as the stack for the application, because it provides a full-stack MVC Framework, supports TypeScript, and follows a convention over configuration environment which helps speed up development. It also provides a very convenient way to create CLI commands that we can use to control aspects of our application, such as starting batch jobs, or triggering specific actions.

In this Mile we need to:

1. Query TezTok and receive the list of OBJKTs. Because the listing is very large, we need to paginate the results with the use of the `limit` and `offset` parameters in the query
2. Store each OBJKT metadata in a local Postgres database, which will serve as the main database of our application.

To achieve this a basic `ArtifactsController` was created, see Figure 5.3.

This concludes iteration RQ1.1. At this stage our database contains the metadata of 21,394 OBJKTs.

Figure 5.3: Mile 4 Architecture

5.4 Iteration RQ1.2

In this section iteration RQ1.2 will be developed, which consists of a single Mile, see Table 5.4.

Iteration	Mile	Description
Iteration RQ1.2	Mile 3	Fetch and pin all OBJKTs of potential interest

Table 5.4: Iteration RQ1.2 Mile

5.4.1 Mile 3 - Fetch and pin OBJKTs

In this Mile we will start pinning the OBJKTs assets in a local IPFS node. This is a significant milestone because from this moment onwards, the system is already delivering a useful service to the ecosystem. By pinning content and participating in the IPFS p2p network we are helping other nodes access the content.

Tasks for Mile 3:

1. Setup an IPFS node (Kubo)⁸ to fetch and pin the OBJKTs
2. For each OBJKT metadata, we instruct the IPFS node to pin the CIDs of that OBJKT. This operation will also automatically fetch the assets to the IPFS node. These operations take a significant amount of time, so we need to queue the operations in a Redis database, which is consumed by a worker that actually communicates with the IPFS node.

At this stage the system architecture is illustrated in Figure 5.4, and after all

⁸<https://github.com/ipfs/kubo>

Figure 5.4: Mile 3 Architecture

OBJKTs are fetched and pinned, the IPFS node is using 79.3GB of disk size.

As a by-product of completing Iteration RQ1.2, the research question RQ3, “what are the disk space requirements for storing all code-based HEN OBJKTs’ media asset”, is already answered.

5.5 Iteration RQ1.3

Iteration RQ1.3 contains 2 Miles, as show in Table 5.5:

Iteration	Mile	Description
Iteration RQ1.3	Mile 2	Run OBJKT in Playwright sandbox and capture traffic
	Mile 1	Analyse traffic and determine if the OBKJT is networked

Table 5.5: Iteration RQ1.3 Miles

5.5.1 Mile 2 - Run OBJKT in sandbox and capture traffic

In this Mile we will use PlayWright to open each OBJKT and record any network calls initiated by the OBJKT. This is done in `SnapshotArtifactService`.

Figure 5.5: Mile 2 Architecture

Snapshots take a significant amount of time, because each snapshot must wait for a few seconds in case an OBJKT makes late network calls. For this reason `ProcessArtifact` had to be run on two different node processes, each one consuming from a separate Redis queue: `ipfs` and `snapshots`.

A significant issue was found at this Mile: the PlayWright library does not release resources when a browser instance is closed, which causes a memory leak after only a short amount of time doing continuous snapshots. This is a known issue, and unlikely to be fixed soon. For this reason, the `ProcessArtifact` process in charge of snapshots must force exit itself after only 5 snapshots, and do this while wrapped in a shell-script which automatically restarts it each time. This way all resources are freed, every 5 snapshots.

```

1 #!/bin/bash
2
3 # Infinite loop to restart the command whenever it exits
4 while true; do
5   # Execute the Node.js command
6   node ace queue:listen --queue=snapshot
7
8   # Wait for a second before restarting to avoid spamming in case of immediate
   failure
9   sleep 1

```

10 `done`

Listing 5.3: runSnapshotWorker.sh

5.5.2 Mile 1 - Classify Networked OBJKTs

At this stage we code the logic that checks whether an OBJKT makes external network requests, and when it does, record that in a `is_networked` database field.

Tasks for Mile 1:

1. Analyse traffic and determine if the OBJKT is networked

After completing this process, we can query the database to find how many OBJKTs are networked. We do want to exclude those which have been burned, or destroyed by their creators, which are normally failed or test mints.

```
1 SELECT COUNT(id)
2 FROM artifacts
3 WHERE is_networked = true
4 AND is_burned = false;
```

Listing 5.4: SQL query - number of networked OBJKTs

As of this writing, there is a total of 1083 networked OBJKTs on the HEN smart contract and each one is properly labelled in our database. RQ1 has been answered.

5.6 Plan for RQ2

We will now turn our attention to RQ2:

RQ2 - Can we capture and document networked HEN OBJKTs aesthetic evolution?

This question is more difficult to answer because we need to define what we mean by “aesthetic evolution”. At its most simplistic level, the regular capturing of screenshots of the artwork might suffice in many instances. But artworks which are animated require a different approach, like a video recording. Others might be

user interactive, and require yet a different strategy, see subsection 6.7.1. External elements, like artist, curator, and conservator documentation, audience reactions, and many others, could also be considered a part of an artwork’s aesthetic evolution. All these would require in-depth classification and analysis of the artwork, which is not feasible within the timeframe of this project. Therefore the scope will be reduced to the content delivered within the OBJKT’s canvas. Also, having in mind the economic sustainability of the project, the decision was made to only take a static screenshot of the artwork during a snapshot to keep the storage space requirements to a minimum.

Therefore the plan for RQ2 only contains one Iteration with one Mile, as show in Table 5.6.

Iteration	Mile	Description
Iteration RQ2.1	Mile 1	Take screenshot of OBJKT during snapshot

Table 5.6: Iteration Plan for RQ2

5.7 Iteration RQ2.1

5.7.1 Mile 1 - Screenshot OBJKT during Snapshot

Since we already have our snapshotting infrastructure in place, all we need is to take a screenshot at the end of the snapshotting process and store it. For now we will store the screenshots as base64-encoded PNGs in our snapshot record. This is not ideal in the long term, as the database will grow quite rapidly, but it works for the purposes of our research question, and that is all that is required when following the RQDD method.

Listing 5.10 shows an abbreviated version of the code which takes the screenshot, using the PlayWright library.

```
1 async snapshot(artifact: Artifact, dryRun: boolean): Promise<void> {
2
3
4   const START_TIME = Date.now();
5
6   // strip ipfs prefix from url
```

```

7   let url = artifact.artifactUri;
8   const pageUrl = this.formatPlatformUrl(artifact, url);
9
10  // prepare browser instance
11  const browser = await chromium.launch();
12  const context = await browser.newContext({
13    viewport: { width: DEFAULT_VIEWPORT_WIDTH,
14              height: DEFAULT_VIEWPORT_HEIGHT
15            }
16  });
17
18  // open artifact URL
19  const page = await context.newPage();
20  await page.goto(pageUrl);
21
22  // wait for the remaining time
23  const TIME_LEFT = SNAPSHOT_DURATION - (Date.now() - START_TIME);
24  await page.waitForTimeout(TIME_LEFT);
25
26  // capture screenshot
27  console.log('Taking screenshot...');
28  const buffer = await page.screenshot({ timeout: 60000 });
29  this.snapshotData.snapshot.screenshot = buffer.toString('base64');

```

Listing 5.5: OBJKT screenshot code

After a round of snapshots with screenshots across all the OBJKTs indexed in our database, the `snapshots` table grew significantly in size, as expected: 26GB. The total database size, including the OBJKTs metadata, is 29.4GB.

A sample of screenshots was manually inspected, and all worked as expected. Later we will develop a web UI where the screenshots can be easily inspected.

This first snapshot is important, as it is used for the initial classification of the OBJKT (networked or not), as well as to establish a baseline record, against which future snapshots can be compared. Therefore it should be taken immediately after discovery/ingestion of new OBJKTs.

This feature allows us to capture screenshots of each OBJKT across time, which answers RQ2, even if in the limited scope that we discussed above.

5.8 Plan for RQ3

RQ3 was answered by Iteration RQ1.2, see section 5.4, page 87.

5.9 Plan for RQ4

RQ4 is the most challenging of all our research questions:

RQ4 - Can an online archive for HEN OBJKTs be economically self-sustainable?

To answer this question we need to understand what are the recurring costs of running such an archive, so that we can calculate the amount of income required to break-even, and then determine if such a source of income can be sustained and how.

Even though this requires mostly a financial analysis, there is a component of development that is required: to create and host an actual online archive. The application developed for the previous RQs already suffices as a backend for such an archive, so all we need is to develop a web-interface that allows for the browsing and searching of the artworks.

Once deployed in production we will determine the recurring cost of hosting the system which will allow us to proceed with the break-even analysis.

This RQ only requires one iteration, see Table 5.7.

5.10 Iteration RQ4.1

Iteration	Mile	Description
Iteration RQ4.1	Mile 2	Develop Web UI
	Mile 1	Deploy system in production

Table 5.7: Iteration RQ4.1 Miles

5.10.1 Mile 2 - Develop Web UI

To develop the web UI we start by sketching a basic wireframe to plan the layout of the pages. We only need 2 page templates, one for browsing the OBJKTs and another to display a particular OBJKT, see Figure 5.6. The browsing page will display 9 artworks at once, with a page navigation control at the bottom. The detail page is somewhat inspired in the Rhizome ArtBase website, with the inclusion of the accordion menus, to show and collapse the details about the artwork.

(a) Artifact Browsing Page

(b) Artifact Detail Page

Figure 5.6: Artifact Web UI Wireframe

With the overall UI mapped out, it was just a matter of coding it, using AdonisJS Edge templating engine. In the Artifact Detail Page, we can see one of the snapshots for the artwork, including the screenshot of the artwork.

For the search facility, a checkbox was added to optionally restrict the search to networked OBJKTs only. This makes use of the automatic classification of networked OBJKTs developed in Iteration RQ1.3 Mile 1.

Also a basic “About” page was created, with a short description of what the project is about. This page also acts as the landing page when a user accesses the main site URL.

The completion of this Mile signals the end of the development phase of this project.

5.10.2 Mile 1 - Deploy System in Production

To deploy the system in production first we need to select a virtual private server (VPS) hosting company that is reasonably priced for our storage needs. The calculation is based on the disk space used in our testing environment.

(a) Artifact Browsing Page

(b) Artifact Detail Page

Figure 5.7: Artifact Web UI Implementation

Description	Space Required (GB)
IPFS	79.0
Database	29.4
Total	108.4

Table 5.8: ARKIVO Storage Requirements

As we can see from Table 5.8, the test instance of our application is using just under 110GB of disk space. Therefore we need to look for a virtual server with 150GB or more of space, to have some spare margin.

After evaluating a number of hosting options, Hetzner⁹ was found to offer the most reasonably priced virtual servers, so it was chosen as the hosting provider for ARKIVO. The CX42 option was selected, which provides the required space, and offers 16GB of RAM, which allows for more caching of assets in RAM when serving content. The cost of this server is EUR 15.90 per month.

⁹<https://www.hetzner.com/cloud/>

Figure 5.8: About Page

NAME	VCPUS	RAM	SSD	TRAFFIC	PRICE / H	PRICE ^
<input type="radio"/> CX22	2 Intel	4 GB	40 GB	20 TB €	€0.005/h	€3.29 /mo
<input type="radio"/> CPX11	2 AMD	2 GB	40 GB	20 TB €	€0.006/h	€3.85 /mo
<input type="radio"/> CX32	4 Intel	8 GB	80 GB	20 TB €	€0.011/h	€6.30 /mo
<input type="radio"/> CPX21	3 AMD	4 GB	80 GB	20 TB €	€0.011/h	€7.05 /mo
<input type="radio"/> CPX31	4 AMD	8 GB	160 GB	20 TB €	€0.021/h	€13.10 /mo
<input checked="" type="radio"/> CX42	8 Intel	16 GB	160 GB	20 TB €	€0.027/h	€15.90 /mo
<input type="radio"/> CPX41	8 AMD	16 GB	240 GB	20 TB €	€0.041/h	€24.70 /mo
<input type="radio"/> CX52	16 Intel	32 GB	320 GB	20 TB €	€0.053/h	€31.90 /mo
<input type="radio"/> CPX51	16 AMD	32 GB	360 GB	20 TB €	€0.087/h	€54.40 /mo

Figure 5.9: Choice of Virtual Server

5.10.2.1 Docker Setup

The application was successfully installed, using Docker containers for all components. An nginx webserver docker container acts as a reverse proxy for the main app and for the IPFS node, and it also handles SSL termination. The SSL certificate was acquired by using the Let's Encrypt Certbot.

Figure 5.10: Docker Containers

In order to ensure that all containers start automatically with each server reboot, it is important to include a `restart: unless-stopped` configuration option for each of the containers in the `docker-compose.prod.yml` file. In Listing 5.1 the `docker-compose` configuration for one of the containers (the IPFS pinning worker node) is listed.

```

1  worker-ipfs:
2    container_name: arkivo_worker_ipfs
3    restart: unless-stopped
4    depends_on:
5      - postgres
6      - redis
7    build:
8      context: .
9      dockerfile: ./docker/worker-ipfs/Dockerfile
10   env_file:
11     - .env
12   environment:
13     - PG_HOST=postgres
14     - REDIS_HOST=redis
15   volumes:
16     - ./:/home/node/app

```

Listing 5.1: Example of a container definition in `docker-compose`

5.10.2.2 Firewall Setup

Another important consideration when deploying the application to a production environment is the implementation of a firewall to restrict access to sensitive ports in the docker setup. By default, all ports exposed by the docker containers are also accessible publicly, even those that should only be used internally between docker containers, and this includes extremely sensitive ports such as the postgres database, redis database, and IPFS management ports. One would expect that installing and configuring the default Ubuntu firewall, UFW, would suffice. However through experimentation this was found not to be the case. Docker and UFW both modify the system's underlying `iptables` rules, resulting in unexpected results. There are methods of configuring UFW with Docker (Jarrousse, 2023)(Feng, 2024), but these include compromises in terms of internal connectivity, are rather complex to setup, and result in a brittle system which could easily break with a simple software update. For this reason the choice was to enable an external firewall solution provided by the VPS host provider as part of the VPS. There is no extra charge for this feature. As shown in Figure 5.11, in addition to the ports specified in Figure 5.10, port 22 was open to allow SSH access to the server. The firewall rules are illustrated in Figure 5.11.

With the firewall in place, and docker containers deployed, `ARKIVO` is live and accessible at: `arkivo.art`

Figure 5.11: VPS Firewall Rules

5.11 Database Schema

There are 5 main tables in the database schema:

1. **artifacts** - the main table for storing the artifact metadata
2. **snapshots** - contains all the snapshots taken. It has a one-to-many relationship with **artifacts**
3. **origins** - contains all the origins (**schema**, **domain**, **port**) that artifacts connect to. It has a many-to-many relationship with **artifacts**, using a pivot table **artifact_origin**
4. **tags** - contains all the tags used by artifacts. It has a many-to-many relationship with **artifacts**, using a pivot table **artifact_tag**
5. **identities** - contains metadata about artists. It should have a many-to-many relationship with **artifacts**, but this was postponed for a future iteration as handling multiple artist OBJKTs (collabs) will require work that is outside the scope of this thesis.

There are also 2 additional tables **adonis_schema** and **adonis_schema_versions** which are used by AdonisJS to manage database schema migrations, and not

relevant for this thesis.

The Entity Relationship Diagram is illustrated in Figure 5.12.

Figure 5.12: Entity Relationship Diagram

5.12 Catalogue Management

Currently the management of the archive's catalogue is all done through CLI on the server, using AdonisJS `node ace` command facility. The following commands were created to facilitate the initialisation of a new ARKIVO instance:

```

1 artifacts:discover           Discovers new artifacts' metadata from
2                             the specified platform, optionally
3                             pinning their payloads
4
5 artifacts:pin                Fetches and Pins already existing
6                             artifacts records
7
8 artifacts:snapshot           Take a snapshot of an artifact

```

```

9
10 artifacts:updateMetadata    Update all token metadata for the
11                             specified platform

```

Listing 5.6: Commands for Catalogue Management

5.13 Other Notes on the Artifact

5.13.1 Webpage metadata

A common issue with most web pages, which can cause considerable annoyance to researchers who are working under tight deadlines, is the fact that they often lack the required metadata that is used by reference management tools, like Zotero, to automatically pull the metadata and populate the bibliographical record.

By default Arkivo suffered from the same problem, so attention was given to resolving this. The `ArtifactController` now prepares a special data structure, `citationMetadata`, with all the required data fields, which is then used by the `header` section of the Edge template. After experimenting with different metadata standards (*Dev:Exposing-metadata [Zotero Documentation]*, n.d.)(Zahid, 2023) , a solution was found using a mixture of standards, where Zotero can pull most of the relevant fields related to an artifact, as shown in Figure 5.13

```

1 <title>{{citationMetadata.title}} - arkivo.art</title>
2 <meta property="og:title" content="{{ citationMetadata.title }}">
3 <meta property="og:type" content="website">
4 <meta property="dc.creator" content="{{ citationMetadata.author }}">
5 <meta property="article:published_time" content="{{ citationMetadata.date }}">
6 <meta property="og:description" content="{{ citationMetadata.description }}">
7 <meta property="og:site_name" content="arkivo.art">

```

Listing 5.7: Artifact page metadata

(a) Before header metadata

(b) After header metadata

Figure 5.13: Artifact metadata pulled by Zotero

5.13.2 Encapsulation of internal IDs

In normal circumstances the listing of a model, like Artifact, would include the unique ID of that model as stored in the database, for example: `/artifacts/45`

However this ID is unique to this instance of the application, and it can change based on the timing of artifact discovery between other instances. For this reason it is imperative that none of the internal IDs generated by the database are exposed to the user.

In order to achieve this, all URLs must be generated using only public identifiers which uniquely identify a model, in the case of an artifact: `blockchain / smart contract / tokenId`. This scheme closely follows existing proposals for cross-chain standardisation of identifiers (Herzog, Gomes, & Thorstensson, 2020).

So what would be a URL:

`/artifacts/2065`

Becomes:

```
/artifacts/tezos/KT1RJ6PbjHpwc3M5rw5s2Nbmefwbuwbdxton/230177
```

However this URL is quite verbose. For convenience, since most of our initial artifacts are all on tezos, and on the HEN's OBJKT smart contract we can:

- omit the blockchain identifier
- use an alias for the smart contract address

This strategy allows us to have shorter, but still unique URLs, which do not expose our internal DB IDs.

```
/artifacts/HEN/230177
```

Even in the cases where a URL is shortened, the long-form URL also works.

5.13.3 Open Source License

This artifact was open sourced under the MIT License. Open sourcing the project is important because anyone should be able to run an instance and replicate the archive. This follows the philosophy behind web3, which was discussed in Motivation chapter.

5.14 Decentralising IPFS Pinning

Although the current server setup has enough storage to hold the catalogue with one full set of snapshots, it does not have enough space for a second round of snapshots, which limits its usefulness in terms of documenting the evolution of the networked artworks. Increasing the size of the VPS is out of the question as it would work against the economic sustainability goal. One potential solution is to decentralise the IPFS pinning of snapshots by running IPFS nodes at home, see Figure 5.14. Such nodes, whilst not enjoying the same bandwidth of a data centre, would still provide a valuable service by pinning the assets, making them available to other, faster, nodes who can cache them. Doing this only for snapshots would ensure that ARKIVO still performed reasonably well when serving the actual web pages with the artwork assets. Off-loading all snapshots would free up nearly

30GB of storage, which constitutes 20% of the total server storage. This would also pave the way to a future decentralised and p2p architecture for ARKIVO, see Figure 5.15.

Figure 5.14: Offload Snapshots to Home Node

The plan is to configure the home node with IPFS, and a script that downloads each snapshot from ARKIVO and adds/pins it to the local IPFS node. Then, after a period of time, ARKIVO can start regularly checking if the CID of each snapshot is available on the IPFS network. When we are confident that the snapshots are regularly available on the IPFS network, then ARKIVO can start to remove them from the PostgreSQL database, leaving only the record ID and the respective IPFS CID.

Figure 5.15: ARKIVO - Towards a p2p Architecture

The hardware acquired was as follows:

Hardware	Cost
Raspberry Pi 4 - 8GB Model	US\$72
2TB SDD	US\$90
DeskPi Pro SDD enclosure	US\$47
Total	US\$209

At current prices this is equivalent to one year's subscription to the ClubNFT service, and we can use this node to pin our personal collection of NFT assets,

ARKIVO snapshots and potentially more.

5.14.1 Assembly of Node Hardware

The assembly of the hardware is relatively straightforward. Some care is required when attaching the heatsink, as the standoffs supplied with the case are very similar but not identical and need to be attached in the right position relative to the Raspberry pi. The following figures illustrate the process:

(a) Apply Thermal Pad to CPU

(b) CPU with Thermal Pad

Figure 5.16: Applying Thermal Pad to CPU

(a) Install CPU Heatsink

(b) Attaching Raspberry Pi to Chassis

Figure 5.17: Attaching Raspberry Pi

(a) Attach cable to TF card adapter

(b) Install SDD

Figure 5.18: Attaching SSD

(a) Insert assembly into case

(b) Close case and remove stickers

Figure 5.19: Completing node assembly

5.14.2 Node Software

The Raspberry SD Card Imager was used to image an SD card (in this case 16GB, but can be 8GB also) with the latest Raspberry Pi OS (64 bit).

The node was then booted with that image, and we used the Raspberry SD Card Imager utility in that installation to image Raspberry Pi OS onto the SSD.

With the operating system now imaged onto the SSD, the node was rebooted, this time removing the SD card (we will no longer be needing it), since now we can boot directly from the SSD.

The DeskPi Pro drivers and services were installed so that they can automatically control the CPU fan based on the temperature sensors built into the Raspberry Pi. The commands used are listed in Listing 5.8.

```
1 sudo apt get update
```

```

2 git clone https://github.com/DeskPi-Team/deskpi.git
3 cd ~/deskpi/installation/RaspberryPiOS/64bit/
4 sudo ./install-raspbios-64bit.sh

```

Listing 5.8: Installation of DeskPi drivers

Docker was installed, as illustrated in Listing 5.9:

```

1 # Add Docker's official GPG key:
2 sudo apt-get update
3 sudo apt-get install ca-certificates curl
4 sudo install -m 0755 -d /etc/apt/keyrings
5 sudo curl -fsSL https://download.docker.com/linux/debian/gpg -o /etc/apt/keyrings
   /docker.asc
6 sudo chmod a+r /etc/apt/keyrings/docker.asc
7
8 # Add the repository to Apt sources:
9 echo \
10 "deb [arch=$(dpkg --print-architecture) signed-by=/etc/apt/keyrings/docker.asc]
   https://download.docker.com/linux/debian \
11 $(. /etc/os-release && echo "$VERSION_CODENAME") stable" | \
12 sudo tee /etc/apt/sources.list.d/docker.list > /dev/null
13 sudo apt-get update
14
15 sudo apt-get install docker-ce docker-ce-cli containerd.io docker-buildx-plugin
   docker-compose-plugin
16
17 sudo groupadd docker
18 sudo usermod -aG docker $USER

```

Listing 5.9: Installation of Docker on Node

After logging out and logging in again to apply the changes, we could then install and run our ARKIVO node snapshot pinning service. It consists of a basic python program that fetches the snapshots of OBJKTs from ARKIVO and pins them to IPFS using a local IPFS node.

```

1 git clone https://github.com/seda-studio/arkivo-node
2 cd arkivo-node
3 docker compose up -d
4
5 sudo apt install screen
6
7 screen -S pinner
8
9 python3 -m venv myenv
10 source myenv/bin/activate
11 pip install ipfshttpclient
12 pip install tqdm
13 python snapshot-pinner.py

```

Listing 5.10: Install and run ARKIVO Node Software

This starts the download and pinning job. Hitting Ctrl + A exits the screen, which leaves the job working in the background.

We can then monitor the progress of the tool in real time with: `tail -f successful_operations.log`.

```

1 SNAPSHOT_ID: 81, CID: QmX47LTHHfQzE8YXytsuj9CtsjN5itecvewmJteJE39haq
2 SNAPSHOT_ID: 83, CID: QmTXwFjt3KQRX8tUxNSVy2gwdovY55WZW3tKHtTTbAtxfK
3 SNAPSHOT_ID: 85, CID: QmdLNwArRE16KV4PmQLnuBNzrTSVfzBsSTRvunEG2Ytcsa

```

```

4 SNAPSHOT_ID: 87, CID: QmRjpTTQfiupUdkM9WCkbruaQorufSmi8CGyF3BWjSF4tP
5 SNAPSHOT_ID: 89, CID: QmTAejhXaqPtCREynYU1RanKhgoLpQgR1z4B2WgJHsnhx8
6 SNAPSHOT_ID: 91, CID: QmXqjX3s3Prexoci1KkZjuZuVN7kmzSia6x6j3EUGp4smK
7 SNAPSHOT_ID: 93, CID: QmTFjJnGihWSbYV3r1NfbTbZEejLXC9SPfYSuHkkxmSAH
8 SNAPSHOT_ID: 95, CID: QmPcGagcfc8YzDd9NuNfFbr8GCmNhwtiD8EvU6863asAWh
9 SNAPSHOT_ID: 97, CID: QmVPruEnfFE8q8NZP6qUzM82CHh5t8CTnA28AmyviEdBgu
10 SNAPSHOT_ID: 103, CID: QmbGqnEejGmd1TxZrAJt3zMHBG765YTQaGZKAED6C36Jd7
11 SNAPSHOT_ID: 105, CID: QmaBbaidtAv5uZUAws1fUrWFRPXMjaLKBEGBpXMR8vcR4b
12 SNAPSHOT_ID: 107, CID: QmTWjVtpmAQyaVNW4t3HA8H989h1wiTDySNUrEUca5Pw69
13 SNAPSHOT_ID: 109, CID: QmW16ZcAAAPdvUFWqfRRV99G2vrqPx21sNSKfXWBEBsMSH

```

Listing 5.11: Output of Snapshot Pinning Job

This node was configured to only pin odd numbered snapshots, because we have a twin node, doing the even numbers.

The power consumption was measured before (idling) and during the pinning operation. Idling the node consumes a steady 5W, and during the pinning it goes up by about 1W, for an average of 6W.

The ARKIVO home node source code, and more detailed installation instructions can be found at: <https://github.com/seda-studio/arkivo-node>

(a) Two Home Nodes Pinning Odd and Even Snapshot IDs

(b) Power Consumption Of One Home Node During Pinning

Figure 5.20: Pinning Snapshots in Home Nodes

5.15 Conclusion

In this chapter a detailed account of the implementation of the artifact was provided, following the RQDD method introduced in chapter 3. This allowed the artifact's development to efficiently answer the research questions. In order to improve the economic sustainability of the artifact, a hardware module was introduced, which allows the pinning of snapshots from home, which allows the

releasing of significant amounts of disk space from the cloud-based installation.

Chapter 6

Artifact Evaluation and Discussion

In this chapter we will evaluate the artifact from three perspectives:

1. Basic web performance metrics;
2. A systematic collection and analysis of the data produced by the artifact;
3. Interviews with stakeholders;

6.1 Web Performance Metrics

Using a website speed tester, we can gather useful information about the performance of the artifact, in terms of loading latency. For this test, Pingdom¹ was used.

Three tests were carried out, one for each of the page types:

1. The about page;
2. The artifacts browsing page;
3. The artifact detail page;

All tests were carried out from Pingdom's North America - USA - Washington DC location.

¹<https://tools.pingdom.com/>

6.1.1 About Page

Page	URL
About	http://arkivo.art/
Full Test	
	https://tools.pingdom.com/#64600c6e88c00000

Table 6.1: Artifacts Browsing - Web Performance Test Details

Figure 6.1: Performance Metric: About Page (Overall)

Improve page performance

GRADE	SUGGESTION
D 67	Compress components with gzip
D 67	Add Expires headers
B 90	Avoid URL redirects
B 90	Use cookie-free domains
A 96	Make fewer HTTP requests
A 100	Avoid empty src or href
A 100	Put JavaScript at bottom

Figure 6.2: Performance Metric: About Page (Improvement Areas)

Figure 6.3: Performance Metric: About Page (Content Breakdown)

Figure 6.4: Performance Metric: About Page (Loading Timeline)

6.1.2 Artifacts Browsing Page

Page	URL
Artifacts Browsing	http://arkivo.art/artifacts
Full Test	
	https://tools.pingdom.com/#64600d6d2400000

Table 6.2: Artifacts Browsing - Web Performance Test Details

Figure 6.5: Performance Metric: Artifacts Browsing Page (Overall)

Improve page performance

GRADE	SUGGESTION
F 45	Add Expires headers
D 67	Compress components with gzip
C 80	Use cookie-free domains
B 90	Avoid URL redirects
A 96	Make fewer HTTP requests
A 100	Avoid empty src or href
A 100	Put JavaScript at bottom

Figure 6.6: Performance Metric: Artifacts Browsing Page (Improvement Areas)

Content size by content type

CONTENT TYPE	PERCENT	SIZE
Image	95.30%	14.1 MB
Error	2.79%	411.2 KB
Script	1.30%	192.6 KB
CSS	0.55%	80.8 KB
HTML	0.06%	9.0 KB
Redirect	0.00%	203.0 B
Total	100.00%	14.8 MB

Requests by content type

CONTENT TYPE	PERCENT	REQUESTS
Image	52.63%	10
CSS	21.05%	4
Script	10.53%	2
Redirect	5.26%	1
HTML	5.26%	1
Error	5.26%	1
Total	100.00%	19

Content size by domain

CONTENT TYPE	PERCENT	SIZE
ipfs.arkivo.art	92.05%	13.6 MB
arkivo.art	6.13%	903.7 KB
arkivo.art:8080	1.18%	173.6 KB
cdn.jsdelivr.net	0.64%	94.1 KB
fonts.googleapis.com	0.01%	835.0 B
Total	100.00%	14.7 MB

Requests by domain

CONTENT TYPE	PERCENT	REQUESTS
ipfs.arkivo.art	42.11%	8
arkivo.art	26.32%	5
cdn.jsdelivr.net	15.79%	3
arkivo.art:8080	10.53%	2
fonts.googleapis.com	5.26%	1
Total	100.00%	19

Figure 6.7: Performance Metric: Artifacts Browsing Page (Content Breakdown)

Figure 6.8: Performance Metric: Artifacts Browsing Page (Loading Timeline) 1/2

Figure 6.9: Performance Metric: Artifacts Browsing Page (Loading Timeline) 2/2

6.1.3 Artifact Detail Page

Page	URL
Artifact Detail	https://arkivo.art/artifacts/HEN/653867
Full Test	https://tools.pingdom.com/#64600ebfd5000000

Table 6.3: Artifact Detail - Web Performance Test Details

Figure 6.10: Performance Metric: Artifact Detail Page (Overall)

Improve page performance

GRADE	SUGGESTION
F 45	Compress components with gzip
D 67	Add Expires headers
B 90	Avoid URL redirects
B 90	Use cookie-free domains
A 96	Make fewer HTTP requests
A 100	Avoid empty src or href
A 100	Put JavaScript at bottom

Figure 6.11: Performance Metric: Artifact Detail Page (Improvement Areas)

Content size by content type

CONTENT TYPE	PERCENT	SIZE
Script	59.75%	911.6 KB
Error	26.95%	411.2 KB
HTML	6.06%	92.5 KB
CSS	5.30%	80.8 KB
XHR	1.89%	28.8 KB
Redirect	0.05%	757.0 B
Image	0.00%	65.0 B
Total	100.00%	1.5 MB

Requests by content type

CONTENT TYPE	PERCENT	REQUESTS
XHR	25.00%	4
CSS	25.00%	4
Script	18.75%	3
HTML	12.50%	2
Redirect	6.25%	1
Image	6.25%	1
Error	6.25%	1
Total	100.00%	16

Content size by domain

CONTENT TYPE	PERCENT	SIZE
ipfs.arkivo.art	49.34%	747.4 KB
arkivo.art	32.92%	498.7 KB
arkivo.art:8080	11.46%	173.6 KB
cdn.jsdelivr.net	6.21%	94.1 KB
fonts.googleapis.com	0.06%	835.0 B
Total	100.00%	1.5 MB

Requests by domain

CONTENT TYPE	PERCENT	REQUESTS
ipfs.arkivo.art	50.00%	8
cdn.jsdelivr.net	18.75%	3
arkivo.art	12.50%	2
arkivo.art:8080	12.50%	2
fonts.googleapis.com	6.25%	1
Total	100.00%	16

Figure 6.12: Performance Metric: Artifact Detail Page (Content Breakdown)

Figure 6.13: Performance Metric: Artifact Detail Page (Loading Timeline)

6.1.4 Web Performance Analysis

The overall performance in terms of latency is good, although there is room for improvement. The initial page load still spends a significant amount of time in the `wait` stage, expire headers are needed, and gzip compression should also be added. Having said that, the assets loaded from the IPFS node performed better than expected.

6.2 IPFS Pinning Verification

One important outcome from developing and launching this artifact, was that it would contribute to the storage and availability of the assets from the artworks which it catalogues, by pinning their CIDs on the IPFS network. To verify that this is the case, one can use online tools which test and report whether a node does indeed do this, such as the IPFS Check tool by Fleek².

Before doing this we need to gather some information, namely our IPFS node PeerID, and the CID of an artwork's asset that we want to test.

²<https://ipfs-check.on.fleek.co/>

For the IPFS node PeerID, we need to gain shell access to the docker container:

```
docker exec -it arkivo_ipfs /bin/sh
```

And then run the command:

```
ipfs id
```

This returns a listing as follows:

```

1 {
2   "ID": "12D3KooWLGnwdHQspFbSSTPSGzarCLL9iQZ4byGfaTpMNfHqBxsA",
3   "PublicKey": "CAESIKFky0Eovy1xWF8BqSpzIi/8CgexN5oNumjWEHg8OKSp",
4   "Addresses": [
5     "/ip4/127.0.0.1/tcp/4001/p2p/12
6       D3KooWLGnwdHQspFbSSTPSGzarCLL9iQZ4byGfaTpMNfHqBxsA",
7     "/ip4/127.0.0.1/udp/4001/quic-v1/p2p/12
8       D3KooWLGnwdHQspFbSSTPSGzarCLL9iQZ4byGfaTpMNfHqBxsA",
9     "/ip4/127.0.0.1/udp/4001/quic-v1/webtransport/certhash/
10      uEiAlIZyEYPy9E79U7avKgVdYjhygiz4Z-0xf8UqEIGQ-BA/certhash/
11      uEiAfDpKQb46669VLVqNw__1QB27Bibr2BGU3QEnZQ4XiBQ/p2p/12
12      D3KooWLGnwdHQspFbSSTPSGzarCLL9iQZ4byGfaTpMNfHqBxsA",
13     "/ip4/167.235.68.63/tcp/4001/p2p/12
14      D3KooWLGnwdHQspFbSSTPSGzarCLL9iQZ4byGfaTpMNfHqBxsA",
15     "/ip4/167.235.68.63/udp/4001/quic-v1/p2p/12
16      D3KooWLGnwdHQspFbSSTPSGzarCLL9iQZ4byGfaTpMNfHqBxsA",
17     "/ip4/167.235.68.63/udp/4001/quic-v1/webtransport/certhash/
18      uEiAlIZyEYPy9E79U7avKgVdYjhygiz4Z-0xf8UqEIGQ-BA/certhash/
19      uEiAfDpKQb46669VLVqNw__1QB27Bibr2BGU3QEnZQ4XiBQ/p2p/12
20      D3KooWLGnwdHQspFbSSTPSGzarCLL9iQZ4byGfaTpMNfHqBxsA",
21     "/ip4/172.18.0.7/tcp/4001/p2p/12
22      D3KooWLGnwdHQspFbSSTPSGzarCLL9iQZ4byGfaTpMNfHqBxsA",
23     "/ip4/172.18.0.7/udp/4001/quic-v1/p2p/12
24      D3KooWLGnwdHQspFbSSTPSGzarCLL9iQZ4byGfaTpMNfHqBxsA",
25     "/ip4/172.18.0.7/udp/4001/quic-v1/webtransport/certhash/
26      uEiAlIZyEYPy9E79U7avKgVdYjhygiz4Z-0xf8UqEIGQ-BA/certhash/
27      uEiAfDpKQb46669VLVqNw__1QB27Bibr2BGU3QEnZQ4XiBQ/p2p/12
28      D3KooWLGnwdHQspFbSSTPSGzarCLL9iQZ4byGfaTpMNfHqBxsA"
29   ],
30   "AgentVersion": "kubo/0.29.0/3f0947b/docker",
31   "Protocols": [
32     "/ipfs/bitstamp",
33     "/ipfs/bitstamp/1.0.0",
34     "/ipfs/bitstamp/1.1.0",
35     "/ipfs/bitstamp/1.2.0",
36     "/ipfs/id/1.0.0",
37     "/ipfs/id/push/1.0.0",
38     "/ipfs/kad/1.0.0",
39     "/ipfs/lan/kad/1.0.0",
40     "/ipfs/ping/1.0.0",
41     "/libp2p/autonat/1.0.0",
42     "/libp2p/circuit/relay/0.2.0/hop",
43     "/libp2p/circuit/relay/0.2.0/stop",
44     "/libp2p/dcutr",
45     "/x/"
46   ]
47 }

```

Listing 6.1: IPFS ID Listing

Our IPFS node ID, which was automatically generated the first time we started the node, appears in line 2:

```
12D3KooWLGnwdHQspFbSSTPSGzarCLL9iQZ4byGfaTpMNfHqBxsA
```

For a CID to test with, we can access an artwork on the system, such as

<https://arkivo.art/artifacts/HEN/8333>, expand the Artifact URIs section, and click the Artifact URI, which opens the artifact's URI on a new window.

Figure 6.14: Finding Artwork IPFS CID (part 1)

The actual IPFS CID appears on the URL, between `ipfs/` and `?creator`.

Figure 6.15: Finding Artwork IPFS CID (part 2)

In this example, the CID is:

`QmaBAatgp6CKJwW6R4xKpNdcmjuzF132erhKExqo4wh6FCV`

With the Peer ID and the artwork's artifact CID, we can access the Fleek IPFS Check tool, and start the check. Making sure to prefix our Peer ID with `/p2p/`:

Figure 6.16: Testing IPFS

As can be verified in Figure 6.16 our node is accessible on the IPFS network, reports that it has the CID, and is also advertising its availability on the networks DHT, making it easier for other nodes to find it.

An additional check we can make is from an independent IPFS node. For example, using the IPFS node in the development server which is located in Macau, we can run a command to find IPFS nodes which are seeding a CID:

```

1 dan@ipfs:~$ ipfs routing findprovs QmaBATgp6CKJwW6R4xKpNdcmjuzF132erhKExqo4wh6FCV
2 12D3KooWAJJJwXsB5b68cbq69KpXiKqQAgTKssg76heHkg6mo2qb
3 12D3KooWLgNwdHQspFbSSTPSGzarCLL9iQZ4byGfaTpMNFHqBxsA
4 12D3KooWEHx9v2SGvFewuatTvzzGxQC1PQQZPRer2ys8fYipiM1zi
5 12D3KooWNTSFywHjGbmGN1aEqJNp54pDKaiwqpthRrvFZETo37pW
6 12D3KooWNTSFywHjGbmGN1aEqJNp54pDKaiwqpthRrvFZETo37pW
7 12D3KooWJ8YAF6DiRrxzcxoeUVjSANYxyxU55ruFgNvQB4EHibpG
8 12D3KooWHEzPJNmo4shWendFFrxDNttYf8DW4eLC7M2JzuXHC1hE
9 12D3KooWgtYkBAaqJMJEywmXaCiNP7LCEFUAFiLEBAsE232c2VH

```

Listing 6.2: Verification of CID availability from external node

As can be seen in Listing 6.2, line 3 shows ARKIVO's IPFS node. It should be noted that seeding peers are not all necessarily pinning the CID. It is simply an indication that those peers currently have a copy of the CID and are making it available to the network, but for some it could be a temporary cache and the CID could be garbage collected by those nodes at any point.

Something else worth noting is that sometimes, even when pinning content, the results from the IPFS check tool may return a failed check relating to multiash missing from the DHT, see Figure 6.17

CID

QmbNtTu7k2E2UDYDQTYiVzV8rVbCU44hc9js1erKzeSogY

Multiaddr

/p2p/12D3KooWLGnwdHQspFbSSTPSGzarCLL9iQZ4byGfaTpMNFHqBxsA

► Optional fields

Run Test

- ✓ Successfully connected to multiaddr:
/ip4/167.235.68.63/udp/4001/quic-v1
- ✓ Found multiaddrs advertised in the DHT:
/ip4/127.0.0.1/tcp/4001
/ip4/127.0.0.1/udp/4001/quic-v1
/ip4/127.0.0.1/udp/4001/quic-v1/webtransport/certhash/uEiAllZyEYPy9E79U7avKgVdYjhygiz4Z-Oxf8UqEIGQ-BA/certhash/
/ip4/167.235.68.63/tcp/4001
/ip4/167.235.68.63/udp/4001/quic-v1
/ip4/167.235.68.63/udp/4001/quic-v1/webtransport/certhash/uEiAllZyEYPy9E79U7avKgVdYjhygiz4Z-Oxf8UqEIGQ-BA/certhash/
/ip4/172.18.0.7/tcp/4001
/ip4/172.18.0.7/udp/4001/quic-v1
/ip4/172.18.0.7/udp/4001/quic-v1/webtransport/certhash/uEiAllZyEYPy9E79U7avKgVdYjhygiz4Z-Oxf8UqEIGQ-BA/certhash/
- ✗ Could not find the multihash in the dht
- ✓ The peer responded that it has the CID

Figure 6.17: Testing IPFS (No DHT)

This is normal, and it is due to the fact that, by default, IPFS nodes only advertise their content every 22h (*Kubo Config File*, 2024), and it may expire from the DHT. Normally this is not a problem, since other nodes, even those not pinning the CIDs, will likely be making them available to the network. There are tradeoffs for increasing the frequency of these provisioning messages, and normally it is a matter of hardware resources. For now we will keep the default value of 22h.

6.2.1 Exhaustive IPFS Pin List Verification

The above checks provide a very basic verification that the system is pinning content, but checking a single CID or even a handful of CIDs manually hardly constitutes a systematic evaluation of the artifact. Therefore another method was employed, which does an exhaustive check, of every CID stored in the system's

database. The process is as follows:

1. export every unique CID from the artifacts stored in the postgres database
2. export every CID pinned by the ipfs node
3. cross check the two data sets to find any discrepancies, such as CIDs present in one dataset but missing from the other

Step 1, involves running the following SQL query:

```

1 SELECT DISTINCT cid AS unique_cid_count
2 FROM (
3     SELECT metadata_uri AS cid FROM artifacts
4     UNION ALL
5     SELECT artifact_uri AS cid FROM artifacts
6     UNION ALL
7     SELECT display_uri AS cid FROM artifacts
8     UNION ALL
9     SELECT thumbnail_uri AS cid FROM artifacts
10 ) AS combined_cids;
```

Listing 6.3: SQL to export all IPFS CIDs store in DB

The database exported dataset contained 47,493 records and was saved as `arkivo-db-cids.txt`. A partial listing of the file is as follows:

```

1 ipfs://QmSbeMcatTg86Yjdva2RW7cQDSZtZWGpCbTMMaYNv44kuA
2 ipfs://QmV6G8cwEbQ1AGeQjCNDNj1kRZq4UBmmRsZi9yRr594vSh
3 ipfs://QmThdTz2LD1u8uoP1zV9qtrfShcm1WSBVXHNfLTLZwHPD
4 ipfs://QmZuBNWdXegm6RFsU7KRxxkqy6G1y2oHiotnZqFPnMFUQx
5 ipfs://QmRuTHQAC3naGCxxPTCTrnrbl0XEbANhNwUwyUsaCwbhfB
6 ...
```

Listing 6.4: Exported CIDs from postgres

Step 2, requires that we export a similar dataset from the IPFS node:

```

1 ipfs pin ls --type=recursive > ipfs-node-pins.txt
```

Listing 6.5: IPFS command to export pinned CIDs

The ipfs node exported dataset contained 46,942 records and was saved as `arkivo-db-cids.txt`. A partial listing of the file is as follows:

```

1 QmRQYgQGFjNJBudPnVEwA3jzBKaDWna943DCdCamdphdJU recursive
2 QmSZ2ieYnJk9PQPrjM5Pe8ieaDfDJZJ58LuV4ijmJtayT recursive
3 QmUYa7jmBaWoGWAT4SdUA1R2kA7kZF4mKzMXhFYn356t2A recursive
4 QmWFjEUGYu6SrzsX3hJ64GHVpfNncvWcgS9EK9hqzt2tmU recursive
5 QmauH5zh1UZjWoFKxQ33MW8YuepvUnUsUqzqoB3Scy6tvq recursive
6 ...
```

Listing 6.6: Exported CIDs from IPFS node

There is a discrepancy of $47,493 - 46,942 = 551$ records which needs to be investigated.

To perform a full cross-check between the two datasets a python program³ was written that automates this process. The program ingests both files, compares

them, and outputs 3 files:

1. `output-arkivo-cids-ok.txt` - all CIDs which are present in both datasets. These are the CIDs which are properly pinned.
2. `output-arkivo-cids-unpinned.txt` - all CIDs present in the database file, but not pinned by the IPFS node. Any records here would be of concern.
3. `output-ipfs-node-unknown.txt` - all CIDs pinned by the IPFS node but not in the database file. Any records here would be odd, and deserved investigation.

After running the python script the results were as follows:

File	Total CIDs
<code>output-arkivo-cids-ok.txt</code>	46,924
<code>output-arkivo-cids-unpinned.txt</code>	569
<code>output-ipfs-node-unknown.txt</code>	18

Table 6.4: IPFS CID Pinning Cross Check Results

6.2.1.1 Analysis of Unpinned CIDs

A preliminary visual examination of `output-arkivo-cids-unpinned.txt` reveals a vast majority of unconventionally formatted entries, or even entries which are not CIDs at all. These correspond to OBJKTs which were not minted via the HEN or Teia UIs, but rather used custom minters or were just minted manually by interacting directly with the HEN smart contract, which anyone can do as the smart contract does not restrict who can interact with it.

```

1 ...
2 QmameE36rswxEQCf6UV53kqsopD3Tprtv6km9rG1UPzHy?seed=tengil
3 QmameE36rswxEQCf6UV53kqsopD3Tprtv6km9rG1UPzHy?seed=8bit
4 QmPVSET5pHD7EwC7KXZy2Bzah9G8UusnzcBQ7ZdcHaG1T?seed=7az2!346fdsg4?
5 QmameE36rswxEQCf6UV53kqsopD3Tprtv6km9rG1UPzHy?seed=
   bolitaeslaperritamasguapadeluniverso
6 QmameE36rswxEQCf6UV53kqsopD3Tprtv6km9rG1UPzHy?seed=amour%20amour
7 QmameE36rswxEQCf6UV53kqsopD3Tprtv6km9rG1UPzHy?seed=purespider
8 javascript:alert('hi');
9 QmameE36rswxEQCf6UV53kqsopD3Tprtv6km9rG1UPzHy?seed=NFTs%20are%20dead
10 QmameE36rswxEQCf6UV53kqsopD3Tprtv6km9rG1UPzHy?seed=Fort%20Gallery%20Nft
11 QmameE36rswxEQCf6UV53kqsopD3Tprtv6km9rG1UPzHy?seed=noisynft
12 QmameE36rswxEQCf6UV53kqsopD3Tprtv6km9rG1UPzHy?seed=TEZOS
13 ...

```

Listing 6.7: Unconventional Format CIDs

³<https://github.com/seda-studio/arkivo/blob/main/utls/ipfs-pin-verification/compare-tool.py>

One type of record consists of CIDs followed by a URL query, such ‘?seed=’. These are custom generative artworks which take a URL parameter as seed. The artist sets up their own website where collectors were able to input their own text as a seed to the artwork, visualise the result, and then collect that iteration as a permanently minted HEN OBJKT.

After manual analysis of the file, 4 instances of this kind of CID were found:

CID	Total records
QmameE36rwswxEQCf6UV53kqsopD3Tprtv6km9rG1UPzHy	430
QmPVSET5pHD7EwC7KXZy2Bzah9G8UusnzcQ7ZdcHaGi1T	62
QmWNkc1ZqEVmFxF7JDLjY4jJefkyhdwxAUegimnxFi4qSr	54
QmVZ59sqM2QVbSXJcb8c4P9Abu35Tq3smfrFJi5VMwA3vo	6
Total	552

Table 6.5: Custom Generative Art CIDs

These 4 CIDs are all from the same artist account⁴, which belongs to generative artist @shig_nft⁵, who created a series of these projects, under the name “Procedural Symbols”. A couple of samples of the artwork are included here:

(a) This belongs in a museum :: Procedural Symbols #61/1000. Source: <https://arkivo.art/artifacts/HEN/230702>

(b) ktorn likes blueeeeeeeeeeeeeeeeeeeeeee :: Procedural Symbols (H=N) #545/1000. Source: <https://arkivo.art/artifacts/HEN/653867>

Figure 6.18: Sample “Procedural Symbols”, which add URL queries to IPFS CIDs

However the artist was also careful to mint each of the above CIDs as well

⁴<https://teia.art/art-o-matic>

⁵https://x.com/shig_nft

formatted CID, without the URL query. This means both HEN, Teia, and now ARKIVO successfully pin them, and therefore those 552 records can be safely ignored as they will all work, as verified by the artworks illustrated in Figure 6.18.

We are therefore left with 17 CIDs unaccounted for:

```

1 k51qzi5uqu5dm198e6gwnuihom8ht49z8u2qu2amjvo32380enkgh8riyrx9
2 javascript:alert('hi');
3 ipns/k51qzi5uqu5dhxiw7jv2i10s3o3xga5bw2wkc945zyvtpk0smrxejx632h11v4/cover.jpg
4 https://ipfs.io/ipns/
   k51qzi5uqu5dhxiw7jv2i10s3o3xga5bw2wkc945zyvtpk0smrxejx632h11v4
5 https://ipfs.io/ipfs/QmadbYeKWMQAiaeTmg9e7M9HQGbVjwsibPpF4rWSr5rhuk/?id=22
6 ipns://k51qzi5uqu5dhxiw7jv2i10s3o3xga5bw2wkc945zyvtpk0smrxejx632h11v4/cover.jpg
7 QmXvAQAcu1wVBCRjSoJsJczkiq18ZQ6XLjgMG7k67pBL8D?id=123
8 ipns://k51qzi5uqu5dhxiw7jv2i10s3o3xga5bw2wkc945zyvtpk0smrxejx632h11v4
9 https://ipfs.io/ipns/
   k51qzi5uqu5dhxiw7jv2i10s3o3xga5bw2wkc945zyvtpk0smrxejx632h11v4/cover.jpg
10 k51qzi5uqu5dhxiw7jv2i10s3o3xga5bw2wkc945zyvtpk0smrxejx632h11v4/cover.jpg
11 Qme1GBYaCfG7ZJjDBppZj4WDbvE94AD7gA5NeyLtKrvdKM?seed=SH!G%20made%20this%20%5C@/
12 QmU7kxXjA8mXRNEZi21joc62fCdYMGVDnErYCYr3EYH4sJ
13 QmfJegSaQ3SicrB6eW2XxUkYfkvvCTNkQKSAZbknmZA6zQ?seed=This is a test!
14 QmVQwyh9hNJPzUmnTYFqY6bvX6PGUGxEyF1w45M9R1Brn
15 undefined
16 ipns/k51qzi5uqu5dm198e6gwnuihom8ht49z8u2qu2amjvo32380enkgh8riyrx9

```

Listing 6.8: 17 Remaining Unconventional Format CIDs

After checking each one, 15 were found to be failed tests, as artists were experimenting with the possibilities. Most belong to OBJKTs which have been burnt by the artists. However 2 CIDs were found to be valid and belong to existing artworks indexed by our artifact.

```

1 QmU7kxXjA8mXRNEZi21joc62fCdYMGVDnErYCYr3EYH4sJ
2 QmVQwyh9hNJPzUmnTYFqY6bvX6PGUGxEyF1w45M9R1Brn

```

Listing 6.9: 17 Remaining Unconventional Format CIDs

Both are thumbnails, belonging to OBJKTs 767305 and 796127, respectively. It is unclear why these 2 CIDs, out of a total 46,924 CIDs, failed to get pinned. The ipfs pinning worker, similarly to the snapshot worker, will re-try an operation 3 times, as per the configuration of the redis queue. However these retries are immediate, and not delayed, so a temporary network issue, or some other problem could have affected these.

Nevertheless, one of the CLI management commands that we developed allow us to issue a pin request for any OBJKT. The syntax for the command is:

```
node ace artifacts:pin <blockchain> <smart-contract-address> <token-id>
```

This command will attempt a pin (or re-pin) of all CIDs associated with an

OBJKT: metadata, artifact, display, and thumbnail.

```

1 # node ace artifacts:pin tezos KT1RJ6PbjHpwc3M5rw5s2Nbmefwbubdxton 767305
2 chain: [tezos]
3 contract: [KT1RJ6PbjHpwc3M5rw5s2Nbmefwbubdxton]
4 token_id: [767305]
5 [ info ] Token sent for processing: 767305
6 #
7 # node ace artifacts:pin tezos KT1RJ6PbjHpwc3M5rw5s2Nbmefwbubdxton 796127
8 chain: [tezos]
9 contract: [KT1RJ6PbjHpwc3M5rw5s2Nbmefwbubdxton]
10 token_id: [796127]
11 [ info ] Token sent for processing: 796127
    
```

Listing 6.10: Command to Pin OBJKT

To verify that the command worked, we tried to access the URLs from our IPFS node before and after running it.

Figure 6.19: OBJKT thumbnail before pin

(a) “Purple Haze - Teddi” by killjoyink.
Source:
<https://arkivo.art/artifacts/HEN/767305>

(b) “Freedom” by Vlas Below art.
Source:
<https://arkivo.art/artifacts/HEN/796127>

Figure 6.20: OBJKT thumbnails after pin retry

With this, we can now conclude that all valid CIDs are successfully pinned by our IPFS node. However we still have 18 CIDs pinned by the IPFS node which are not in our database, therefore unaccounted for.

6.2.1.2 Analysis of Unknown CIDs

The list of 18 unknown CIDs is as follows:

```

1 QmVi33nTqwUZbL64d7Ab9EPPW4npmQRxMhE1E8VQnQZsHf
2 QmaxptTRV7we3QubVsiNcpSf74zmCrsKrXYS1wH6NfjHDm
3 QmYBWDdBpQwP1QgPZo94Mx8VM6XNr2xRmpVhAcLrHhZNhd
4 QmU9eBL6T7zAGV48o462LDvB4YPNnYjpmgQDQaB7PTboNP
5 QmdcamM7GogJxh3uBQkoGkw7CpJzghbVubFknvTw9tNPPm
6 QmacVsiszqR49aqeKaxWCVBuD77mbKh9xf2CRnVJ6aPkrQq
7 Qmd5mT8GYEeDp2zG5jqEndZKoqn882FMzcbFmYdhxzrubbz
8 QmZRUBYUdfsT1oWzD91ZdHbnrBsaSY78awYoB9ihAfn3df
9 Qmd8w32fPqa1niDQpQqooxznhB5qjsFdmw713pcDcaV6VW
10 QmTHGKahi8bG4W6MV4bsvjSpgr6DThiWP9LbhT1extuwpU
11 QmPgLv9BVygyPy3x3C3qNWGWJoJZtDD5P4JAVXq6g7siG9
12 QmTCaF4prs5ndNVsBoCsHGHBRYyLLKQeryTyA6hDtMTk1R
13 Qme1GBYaCfG7ZJjDBppZj4WDbvE94AD7gA5NeyLtKrvdKM
14 QmcSfymXa4rgip9QdqmP8xFNERBmLdWzd3vGkN7QxMR75
15 QmRzvn7672UYPniAvz4ofh9dmDNF2NvjEeyBtBEvbcuQ29
16 QmYuApfJaKy8tcMCrjgJQ8nGMdqrq75kQ5qA5aSikCD96F
17 QmVp8W3xQCCFU4PHrUQgyb4yfFeR1SL3gM2xtvS6sdEiK8
18 QmUNLLsPACCz1vLxQVkXqQLX5R1X345qqfHbsf67hvA3Nn

```

Listing 6.11: Command to Pin OBJKT

Two of the CIDs were done manually as a means to test the IPFS node, so are accounted for. However the 16 remaining ones are unknown, and the vast majority seem to be trailers for a Chinese TV soap opera. The most plausible theory is that, during the deployment of the artifact in production, a few hours elapsed in which the firewall was not yet in place, and remote nodes were able to access our node's private API port (5001) and remotely requested the pinning of those CIDs.

Since we already have the firewall in place now, it is just a matter of cleaning those CIDs from our node, which we did with the command: `ipfs pin rm <CID>`, followed by a `ipfs repo gc` to garbage collect any remains of CIDs which should not be there.

Additionally, we enabled the option `NoFetch = true` on the IPFS node configuration, which ensures our node only serves content which is explicitly pinned, and will not attempt to fetch any other CIDs requested via the public gateway. Only requests from our application, via the (now private) API port will pin new content to our node.

This was an invaluable, as well as slightly comical, lesson and reminder on how to deploy IPFS nodes, or any other application for that matter: have the firewall in place *before* deployment!

6.2.2 Verifying IPFS Data Integrity

Verifying that all CIDs are pinned is only half of the work. We also need to check the data integrity of all pinned content on the node. To achieve that, IPFS offers a command which exhaustively checks the data integrity of every pinned CID: `ipfs pin verify`. This command can take some time to complete, with over 46000 CIDs to verify, for that reason the command was prefixed by `time` to determine how long it takes to execute.

```
1 / # time ipfs pin verify
2 real 5m 30.82s
3 user 0m 0.07s
4 sys 0m 0.05s
```

Listing 6.12: Internal IPFS pin verification

As can be seen in Listing 6.12, it ran in 5m30s and returned no errors, therefore our storage's integrity is verified.

6.3 Snapshot Verification

Verifying the validity of the snapshots is significantly more difficult, because many things could go wrong unnoticed, for example a screenshot could fail to capture the rendering of the artwork.

1. Verify that every artifact has one, and only one, snapshot recorded in the database;
2. Perform a systematic visual check of the screenshots
3. Perform a manual verification that the classification of artworks as networked is correct

6.3.1 Snapshot Record Integrity Verification

Here we want to run a SQL query that verifies that each artifact in the database has exactly one snapshot.

The first query we run checks if any artifacts do not have a snapshot:

```

1 SELECT COUNT(id)
2 FROM artifacts
3 WHERE id NOT IN (
4     SELECT DISTINCT artifact_id
5     FROM snapshots
6 );

```

Listing 6.13: SQL - Check Missing Snapshots

And unfortunately we have a total of 174. Similarly to the IPFS pinning worker, our snapshotting worker retries 3 times before giving up, so something wrong must be happening with these artifacts.

After exporting the list of `token_ids` affected, another batch of snapshots was started, just for those artifacts. It became clear that something is indeed preventing these artifacts from getting snapshotted, with Playwright reporting several timeout errors. A visual inspection of a selection of the artifacts proved that it was loading on the web UI, so the IPFS asset was present in the system. One observation was that all these artifacts were quite *heavy* in terms of CPU load, making the fan on the computer spin up. This could be an indication of the problem. After the batch of snapshots completed, the SQL query was retried and this time the number went down to 164. This means 10 artifacts out of 174, succeeded in getting snapshotted this time around.

Since we are indexing and hosting 21,390 artifacts, 164 represents only 0.766% of the total, so it was decided that the snapshots for these artifacts would have to be revisited at a later stage.

The reverse query was then used to find artifacts that may have more than one snapshot.

```

1 SELECT COUNT(*)
2 FROM (
3     SELECT artifact_id, COUNT(*) AS snapshot_count
4     FROM snapshots
5     GROUP BY artifact_id
6     HAVING COUNT(*) >= 2
7 ) AS subquery;

```

Listing 6.14: SQL - Check Duplicate Snapshots

This returned a surprising count of 4345. A quick follow-up query revealed 13 artifacts with 3 snapshots each, followed by a long tail of artifacts with 2 snapshots. This represents nearly 20% of all artifacts having more than one snapshot. Since only one batch of snapshots was run, this could mean that there is an issue on the snapshot retry logic. A note was taken of this for future troubleshooting, and the duplicate snapshots were removed:

```
1 DELETE FROM snapshots
2 WHERE id NOT IN (
3     SELECT id FROM (
4         SELECT id,
5             ROW_NUMBER() OVER (PARTITION BY artifact_id ORDER BY created_at
6                                 DESC) AS rn
7         FROM snapshots
8     ) AS ranked
9     WHERE rn = 1
10 );
```

Listing 6.15: SQL - Deleting Duplicate Snapshots

This concluded the basic snapshot record integrity check. Now we need to look into the actual content of the snapshots.

6.3.2 Snapshot Visual Verification

At a first glance the snapshot seems to have identified the external network call, and ignored the internal ones. It also captured the screenshot well. The full snapshot download worked as well. To verify that the network call was well identified it was run with the browser's developer tools open.

Figure 6.21: Sample Snapshot

Additionally, the automatic classification was checked for correctness. It also passed, see Figure 6.22.

Tags	∨
Classification	∧
JavaScript	true
Networked	true
Links	∨

Figure 6.22: Sample Classification

After this initial check a systematic verification took place. For every 50 pages of results, the first artifact on the page was checked following the same procedure as above. A total of 36 artifacts were manually verified and all passed the test.

At this stage we were ready to involve stakeholders in the evaluation of the artifact.

6.4 Stakeholder Feedback

Several stakeholders were contacted, via twitter and discord, however due to lack of time, only six participated. Three via a written evaluation form, and three agreed to be interviewed remotely via Discord and Google Meet.

6.4.1 Evaluation Form

The goal of the evaluation form was to help validate the classification capabilities of the artifact, as well as gather feedback about potential areas of improvement. The evaluation form can be found in Appendix 4, page 164.

All three participants knew networked OBJKTs, were able to find them, and reported that the system correctly classified.

Similarly, all three reported the successful classification of a code-based non-networked OBJKT.

As far as what features they would like to see implemented, the following were mentioned:

- Dark mode

- Making tags browsable (currently they are only text)
- Allow logging in with wallet, to visualise 'owner' specific versions of the artifacts
- Option to only run an artifact after checking its list of network calls (for security purposes)
- Only show "about page" as landing page the first time, then default to catalogue (using local storage)
- Show how many results a search returned

One participant also mentioned that snapshots need more explanation. "Is it just a image snapshot? Does it store the returned metadata by every query that the OBJKT does? Where are the snapshots stored? IPFS? How can I access them? How are snapshots triggered? Regularly for all tokens? Are they triggered differently for different tokens?" (Participant)

Another participant suggested that we replace the "black" thumbnails with actual thumbnails (potentially from snapshot screenshots).

One participant reported the Metadata URL not working. This is because it was using the `ipfs://` prefix. It has now been fixed.

Overall they found the design and functions user friendly. They could find their way easily.

"Nice and clean interface, not cluttered, intuitive UI and easy to use" (Participant)

6.4.2 Interviews

The interviews were conducted in a semi-structured way, starting with a walk-through of the artifact, and letting the participant explore the system. Then a general discussion about code-based crypto art would take place, with the researcher sometimes nudging the participant with questions about the long-term preservation.

In general the system was received with enthusiasm, with one participant high-

lighting how important it is that this artifact focuses on HEN artworks, because of its cultural significance.

One of the participants reiterated that snapshots need a bit more explaining, similarly to what had been mentioned by one of the evaluation form participants.

Another participant mentioned that they would like to see a space where manual documentation can be added, either by the artist or by conservators, or both. "We need a document" (Participant).

One of the questions asked was whether artists care about the type of restoration approaches. The participant believes that artists are generally more flexible about the types of intervention than conservators.

One of the participants explained that not every aspect of an artwork can be open source, and thus for long term preservation a "conservation package" should be prepared to share with a museum or another cultural institution.

An interesting topic of discussion was the need for a cross-platform standard for networked artworks. Allowing artworks to query certain kinds of data from its hosting platforms.

One participant reminded that artworks should always have a "fall-back" static version, if the network fails.

A participant expressed their wish for a hardware device that users can host at home for pinning their own collections.

The participants agreed that there is a need for a conversation between artists, conservators, and platforms, about the way best way forward for preservation.

On participant stated the importance for this work, because networked crypto art is "the most native art form to the blockchain" (Participant).

6.5 Data Volume Trend

In this section we will extract and analyse data from the artifact, with the goal of gaining insights into the future storage requirements of ARKIVO. Firstly we will

look at the trend in terms of data stored over time.

Figure 6.23: IPFS Storage Over Time (Code-Based OBJKTs)

As can be seen in Figure 6.23, there has been a significant slowing down of growth in terms of storage requirements, which is positive from a cost of storage perspective. Since ARKIVO does not store market data, it is impossible to determine how this compares to the slowing down in market activity.

ARKIVO: Networked vs Non-Networked (Number of Tokens)

Figure 6.24: Networked vs Non-Networked (Number of Tokens)

ARKIVO: Networked vs Non-Networked (Total Artifact Size in GB)

Figure 6.25: Networked vs Non-Networked (Artifact Size)

Figure 6.24 reveals that networked OBJKTs constitute a minority in terms of number of tokens minted, with only 6.5% of tokens, however that figure more than doubles if we analyse it from an artifact size perspective, see Figure 6.25. This suggests that even though small in relative number, network OBJKTs are on average larger in size.

This data shows that it is feasible for ARKIVO to continue running on its current infrastructure, especially if we are able to offload snapshots to home nodes.

6.5.1 Burned OBJKTs

It must be noted that there is a discrepancy between the total number of tokens shown in Figure 6.24 (16,652) and the total number of tokens originally reported in subsection 5.3.2 (Mile 4 - Query TezTok, page 85), 21,394. This discrepancy is due to the fact that these graphs exclude burned OBJKTs, which are 4,742 in total.

A burned OBJKT is one that the artist intentionally removed from circulation, by transferring all editions to a well known *burn* address. This address is not controlled by anyone, and therefore the editions are considered to be inaccessible,

and can never be traded again. Aside from burning whole OBJKTs, it is also possible to only burn a fraction of the editions of an OBJKT, reducing its supply of editions. This action does not flag the OBJKT itself as burned.

6.6 Archiving ARKIVO

As discussed in subsection 2.2.4, page 32, Teia’s current UI prevents the WayBack Machine from successfully capturing the OBJKTs displayed on each page. By employing a simpler Web UI, ARKIVO allows such archiving. As an example we requested the capture of “Generative Abstract Series 012” by Yazid via the ARKIVO page, and the capture completed successfully, see Figure 6.26. This gives artworks catalogued by our system a chance of gaining yet another archival copy, and these copies could even outlast ARKIVO itself.

6.7 Discussion

The following sections will provide additional discussion of relevance to this project.

6.7.1 Capturing Interactive Artworks

One of the challenges of automating the aesthetic capture of user-interactive artworks is determining the ways in which they can be interacted with. As discussed in section 4.2, interactions can take many forms. However a manual non-exhaustive sampling of OBJKTs indexed by ARKIVO suggests that mouse and keyboard interactions are the most common forms of interaction in this dataset. Tools like PlayWright can simulate mouse and keyboard input during the snapshotting process, so in theory it should be possible to capture this kind of interaction. However the biggest challenge in achieving automatic interaction without any prior knowledge of the artwork is determining where in the screen to click or

Figure 6.26: Generative Abstract Series 012 by Yazid, a snapshot of Arkivo by WayBackMachine

which keys to press. Also depending on the nature of the artwork, the interactions could be quite complex.

However a very basic experiment was attempted, using ChatGPT, to determine if a piece is interactive, and if so, where in the screen to click. As an example, the “Jumpy Dot” artwork by mrdoob was used.

After uploading the screenshot, the following prompts, designed to be generic and applicable to all artworks indexed by ARKIVO, were used:

1. examine this image, and tell me if you think this represents an interactive interface
2. if I were to click on the image to interact with it, give me approximate x,y coordinates where I should click

The full ChatGPT chat with prompts and responses can be found in Appendix 3, page 162.

ChatGPT successfully identified the 'start' button and thus correctly classified the artwork as interactive. It also provided the following X,Y coordinates for click it: 255, 350

As can be seen in Figure 6.27, the coordinate provided by ChatGPT was relatively close, but failed to hit the 'start' button.

Figure 6.27: ChatGPT estimated interaction coordinate

It should be noted that this artwork, due to the simplicity its the interface, and the explicit nature of the 'start' button, constitutes one of the easiest possible tests for an LLM like ChatGPT to determine interactivity and hotspot locations for interactions. The fact that it failed to provide the correct coordinate suggests there is still a gap between the textual description of the location of the button, "close to the center horizontally [...] slightly below the center vertically" and the prediction of the coordinate.

The LLM approach to UI interaction is fairly new, but some research is starting emerge (Liu et al., 2024), and more is expected to follow.

Alternative strategies for interacting with the artwork can also be experimented with. For example, the Android development ecosystem has a tool, UI/Application Exerciser Monkey, which generates pseudo-random streams of user events such as

clicks, touches, or gestures for automated UI testing (*UI/Application Exerciser Monkey* | *Android Studio*, n.d.).

6.7.2 Cost of Storage

Currently, the cost of minting an OBJKT on the HEN contract constitutes a fraction of the cost of hosting and/or pinning 2GB of data. This represents a loophole that could be exploited by malicious actors, or freeloaders, making the pinning of assets hosted by Teia unfeasible without a significant recurring investment, which impacts the economic sustainability of the project.

6.7.3 Emulation

As time passes, technology will continue to evolve. New hardware will run new operating systems, which will run new web browsers, or even totally paradigm changing *content rendering applications* which may replace web browsers in the future. This means that in long term it seems inevitable that all code-base artworks created today, even those based on web standards and without any network dependencies, will require some form of hardware and/or browser emulation to render successfully.

This inevitable evolution into emulated environments does represent an additional challenge for networked artworks, because in addition to emulating the artefact's code-base itself, the emulation environment must also simulate the network dependencies of the artwork, and this can pose a problem known to software developers as *dependency hell*, where each dependency in turn depends on a number of other dependencies, leading to an ever increasing dependency tree. A solution to this problem seems unfeasible, if any of those dependencies, or their sub-dependencies, does not strictly follow the web3 architecture that makes projects easily duplicable.

For this reason, Inversion of Control (IoC) (Fowler, 2005) and Dependency Injection (DI) (Martin, 1994) models, popular in software development as a way to

de-couple software components, gain an even greater importance for the longevity of code-based networked artworks, because you can more easily generate the data expected by the artwork, or in the worst-case scenario, simply repeatedly inject the last known good snapshot of data for all future renderings.

6.7.4 Beyond the Canvas

All of the artworks which this project currently aims to cater for in terms of conservation have one thing in common: their visual rendering is restricted to the boundaries of an HTML element on a web page, the canvas. Even those which intentionally choose to spread their visual expression past the boundaries of a single canvas element, are still constrained by the larger HTML DOM object or web page in which they, as web-based artworks, essentially exist. This is not unique to digital art. The great majority of paintings displayed in traditional museums are also constrained by their physical framed canvasses. Sculptures and other art installations are exceptions to this rule. However networked art reaches out into the world, and it would seem appropriate to explore a rendering medium that represents that breaking away from the canvas.

6.7.5 Identifying IPFS Pinning Abuse

Since most IPFS pinning services are paid for, there is a potential for abuse of free pinning services like Teia, and now Arkivo, by mining directory-x OBJKTs just as a way to store data on IPFS for free. The OBJKT might even render a piece of original art, but just as a facade for a much larger data payload. This would add to an archive's storage costs without contributing back in terms of donation, hurting its sustainability.

6.8 Conclusion

This chapter provided a detailed and systematic evaluation of the artifact from several angles, such as web performance, IPFS pinning validation and stakeholder feedback. Several areas of improvement were identified, which will be addressed in future iterations of the project. The stakeholder feedback was particularly useful and encouraging as it validated the choice of topic of the study.

Chapter 7

Conclusion

This chapter concludes the study by reviewing what was accomplished and how it relates to the initial goals of the project. It also describes the main ideas reserved for future work.

7.1 Review of Objectives

As stated in chapter 1, this work had two main objectives:

- To design and implement a sustainable IS that can support the long-term preservation of networked crypto art
- To contribute to the body of knowledge in the area of networked crypto art conservation

These objectives were then broken down into 4 research questions:

- RQ1 - Can we determine which code-based HEN OBJKTs are networked?
- RQ2 - Can we capture and document networked HEN OBJKTs aesthetic evolution?
- RQ3 - What are the disk space requirements for storing all code-based HEN OBJKTs' media assets?
- RQ4 - Can an online archive for HEN OBJKTs be economically self-sustainable?

With the development of ARKIVO we were able to answer these questions:

RQ1 - ARKIVO is able to classify which code-based artworks are networked, and as far as we could test it has a perfect success rate (100%).

RQ2 - the snapshot feature in ARKIVO can capture an OBJKT's aesthetic evolution, and in the process document it. A question remains about the disk space requirements for regular snapshots, however with the introduction of the Home Nodes, this problem may already be solved

RQ3 - this question was answered in subsection 5.4.1 (Mile 3 - Fetch and pin OBJKTs, page 86): 79.3GB space on disk.

RQ4 - this question is the most challenging, because to be economically sustainable the platform would need to break even financially, yet currently it has no sources of funding. The effort to decentralise the snapshots by a network of home nodes should go a long way towards achieving this goal, but the project also needs to receive a regular source of funding, and the concept of royalty splits contributing to the project, in a VDP style, is something we would like to encourage.

Archiving all code-based HEN OBJKTs at a monthly cost of EUR 15.90 provides a useful data point on the sustainability of small scale digital archives, and is one of the contributions of this project to the body of knowledge.

7.2 Recommended Best Practices

When creating a networked crypto artwork, artists should have in mind the following best practices:

- Use defensive programming techniques, so that your code does not fail in unexpected ways. Add fall-back mechanisms at several key points so that the piece will degrade gracefully rather than break unexpectedly;
- In the worst case scenario, when all else fails, have one last fall-back mechanism so that the piece renders a static version that is aesthetically pleasing;
- When an error does occur, make it clear on the console log.
- Add an overlay menu that the user can pull up to re-configure external

dependency URLs. Save these settings in Local Storage so that the user does not have to re-input them every time they access the piece;

- Add documentation within the artwork’s assets directory. This should be in a plain-text document, describing the piece in detail. Technical details such as native display resolution, orientation, etc. Also it should include samples of expected data returned by network dependencies and how they are used by the artwork;

7.3 Future Work

This work laid the foundation for future work in the area of code-based crypto art preservation. Some of the ideas for such work are as follows:

- Study methods of automatically classifying the artworks according to the taxonomy proposed in section 4.2 (page 74). This work could potentially employ the use of Large Language Models (LLMs);
- Implement a thorough security scan of the artwork’s code, using a variety of methods, as described in subsection 2.5.2 (Code Security, page 48);
- Integrate the WARC file format into the snapshot feature, so that snapshots comply with this industry standard;
- Allow users to login with their crypto wallets so as being able to experience owner specific versions of the artworks;
- Create a staging area for collaborative documentation, between artist and curator, which can be published to the blockchain when finalized;
- Create an area for restoration of broken artworks;

7.4 Personal Remarks

ARKIVO is very different from existing digital art archives in the sense that it is currently an automated platform. There is no manual acquisition of artworks, nor curation of listed OBJKTs. Every newly minted code-based OBJKT is automati-

cally indexed and added to the archive. This was intentional, as it contributes to a lower cost of running the platform. This approach is not meant to diminish the role of human conservators. Much the opposite. In its limitations it highlights the important role that human conservators play in the preservation of digital art.

This study aimed to deal with the mutable dependency dilemma, by creating a way to document the evolution of artworks which are, a priori, destined to break. Whilst this is a worthwhile endeavour, another approach may be to avoid the dilemma altogether and embrace mutability from the outset. The blockchain's history may be immutable, but the chain itself is changing with each new block. Why not adopt the idea of a mutable artwork, which can not only be patched, but which can be even more fundamentally evolved by its creator? This is a conversation that needs to take place within the crypto art community. As a proof-of-concept, the author developed a simple smart contract on the Tezos blockchain which can act as a basic version control system for an artwork, allowing the artist to evolve the codebase of the piece. In August 2024, the first artwork using this system was minted by the author on the Teia platform, named "This is an evolving artwork" (ktorn, 2024). Originally minted as a simple PNG static image (v1), it was quickly updated to display a different static image (v2), see Figure 7.1, and has subsequently evolved to a p5js codebase (v3) that randomly displays the name of one of its collectors each day, see Figure 7.2. To achieve this, it makes network calls both to determine the current list of collectors' names and to retrieve the hash of the first block from the Tezos blockchain that day, which it uses as a random seed to select a name at random. This means the artwork evolves across 2 dimensions, via the network in an automated fashion, and via the codebase when the author intervenes.

ARKIVO can then automatically document the full evolution of the artwork, via its periodic snapshots. It is the author's hope that these efforts into preservation of networked crypto art can encourage more artists to experiment with this kind of art, as well as give collectors more confidence when considering to add

such artworks to their collections.

Figure 7.1: v1 and v2 of This is an evolving artwork by ktorn, Source: <https://arkivo.art/artifacts/HEN/856725>

Figure 7.2: Multiple outputs from v3 of This is an evolving artwork by ktorn, Source: <https://arkivo.art/artifacts/HEN/856725>

Glossary

abstract syntax tree

a hash of a file, or a chunk of a file, which uniquely identifies that file or chunk on the InterPlanetary File System network, and which can be used to retrieve it via content addressing

code is law

a term coined by Lessig (2009), represents a philosophical stance where aspects of governance and rules that mediate interactions between agents (human or not) are encoded as software and are executed algorithmically, without recourse to subjective interpretations of those rules, resulting in algorithmic and irreversible verdicts of *truth*

conceptual art

an art movement where the concept or idea behind an artwork is more important than the aesthetics of the finished piece

content identifier

a hash of a file, or a chunk of a file, which uniquely identifies that file or chunk on the InterPlanetary File System network, and which can be used to retrieve it via content addressing

decentralised autonomous organisation

an web3 inspired form of organisational structure with no central governing body and whose members share a common goal of acting in the best interest of the entity

decentralised application

an application that runs on a blockchain, normally coded in one or more smart contracts

decentralised finance

an ecosystem of financial instruments, platforms and services, which are built upon blockchains and decentralisation principles, such as transparency, no central authority, trustlessness, censorship-resistance, self-custody, and others

InterPlanetary File System

a decentralised file system project, which uses content addressing rather than location/IP addressing to store and retrieve files

directed acyclic graph

a data structure where nodes connect by directed edges, and these edges do not form any closed loops

distributed hash table

a decentralised key-value store that runs on a p2p network

emulation

the process of imitating the behavior of one system using another system

fungible token

in the context of blockchain, a digital asset issued and controlled by a smart contract or native to a blockchain, constituted by a large number of interchangeable and divisible tokens, and to which economic value is normally attributed by its holders, for example: cryptocurrencies are fungible tokens. often also referred to as *coins*

ghost chain

a blockchain that sees very low user activity, as measured by the volume of on-chain transactions

initial coin offering

a fundraiser strategy for blockchain projects, in which investors receive tokens created by that project

minting

the act of creating a new token on a blockchain, which can either be a fungible token (such as a new coin), or a non-fungible token (NFT) which represents a particular asset, such as an artwork

non-fungible token

a digital and cryptographically signed record created and stored on a blockchain which contains meta-data relating to a unique asset, which it represents. This token is often used as a title of ownership of said asset, which can be traded, transferred, or destroyed

peer-to-peer

a distributed architecture for organising nodes in a network, where they connect and communicate in a mesh-like topology, without relying on central servers

open archival information system

a decentralised file system project, which uses content addressing rather than location/IP addressing to store and retrieve files

primary market

the market where an artwork is sold for the first time, from the artist directly to the first collectors of that artwork, such that the artist sets the price and receives the full proceeds of the sale, minus any marketplace fees

OBJKT

the name of the tokens minted on the Hic et Nunc (HEN) NFT smart contract. This name was later appropriated by the marketplace objkt.com

primary sales

initial sales of an artwork on the primary market

proof-of-stake

a blockchain consensus mechanism where the next validator to produce a block is chosen via a lottery system, where the chance of winning the lottery is proportional to the amount of cryptocurrency staked by each validator

proof-of-work

a system where an agent must provide evidence that a significant amount of computation took place, before they are allowed to take a particular action, and is often used as a way to deter spam and also as a consensus mechanism in some blockchains

research question driven development

a novel research method where the iterative development of an artifact revolves around the answering of research questions

secondary market

the market where an artwork is re-sold, from a collector to another collector, such that the seller sets the price and receives the majority of the proceeds of the sale, minus any artist royalties which are paid to the artist

secondary sales

re-sales of an artwork on the secondary market

web3

a new iteration of the World Wide Web which incorporates concepts such as decentralisation, blockchain technology, and token-based economics

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Appendix 1 - Publications

Farinha, D. F. (2022). A Critical Look at Blockchain-Interactive Generative Art. *International Journal of Creative Interfaces and Computer Graphics (IJCICG)*, 13(1), 1-17.

Abstract

Artists are increasingly using blockchain as a tool for trading digital artwork as non-fungible tokens (NFTs), however some are also beginning to experiment with the blockchain as a medium for generative art, using it as a seed for a generative process or to continuously modify an evolving piece. This paper surveys, reviews and classifies the state-of-the-art in blockchain-interactive NFTs and presents a liberal-arts critique of the opportunities and threats posed by this technology, whilst addressing existing criticism on the broader topic of art-related NFTs. The paper examines some of the most experimental pieces minted on the Hic et Nunc (HEN) and Teia NFT marketplaces, for which a purpose-built research tool was developed. The survey reveals some reliance on centralised infrastructure, namely blockchain indexers, placing undesired trust on third parties which undermines the potential longevity of the artwork. The paper concludes with recommendations for artists and NFT platform designers for developing more resilient and economically sustainable architectures.

Estadiou, G. V., Ng, S. O. K. M., Martins De Abreu, F., & Farinha, D. (2023, November). Beyond Physical Boundaries-Organising a Virtual Exhibiton with NFTs for an International Conference. In *Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on Digital and Interactive Arts* (pp. 1-5).

Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic has challenged individuals and all international collaborations, including research and academic international conferences. Most conferences had to adapt to an online or hybrid mode at best, if not cancelled or postponed. During this period, we were invited to organise the third edition of an international conference on Arts, Technology and Society. At its core, it is an academic conference, but it also offers a platform for an art exhibition and forum for artists to share and exhibit. Due to Macao's physical constraints and its inaccessibility for outside visitors, the Local Organising Committee took the challenge to organise the first virtual art exhibition in an academic conference, including Non-Fungible Tokens (NFT) for artists willing to sell their digital artwork. This paper presents the creative process as well as the technical issues faced during the conference and exhibition preparation time. As NFT-based virtual exhibition is a new offer within an academic international conference and a new tool to permanently promote artists' work, we are also proposing some possible future works to develop further this approach and give it a larger visibility. We believe such type of exhibition can play an important role on a world seeking for more sustainable communication.

Appendix 2

Chainleft's Taxonomy Descriptions

Full descriptions of Chainleft's Taxonomy, provided by private message in Discord.
Included with permission.

“Auto-Evolving

Since EVM can run and calculate data constantly, these calculations can evolve the art itself. The parameters that create the artwork iterate over time to result in a more complex pattern. The difficulty in achieving this comes from new layers of parameters for the evolution that would aesthetically or conceptually still please & produce qualia.

Ever-Changing

We could probably combine the evolution and ever-changing as a single category. However while evolutions tend to reach a level where the art's final goal is fulfilled, ever-changing runtime art fully explores the foreverness of the blockchain runtime. The calculations simply never end.

Programmable

So far we've looked at how the virtual machine's ceaseless work carries the art forward, but what about human agency? This is where programmability comes in. Several runtime art collections allow their collectors (and sometimes other agents!) to influence the artwork. This is

sometimes within the confines of the limits that the artist determines, and sometimes complete freedom where the new work replaces the old one fully.

Social Coordination

If there's one thing that's very blockchain-native, that's coordination. Even the validators that produce the blocks coordinate to make this system live. So some artists used social coordination mechanisms through smart contracts that resulted in artwork being produced through the activities of their collectors.

This is a relatively less explored sub-niche of runtime art, but I think it can get quite exciting when combined with the future of gaming NFTs.

Ownership Aesthetics

Ownership has been a major concept in the NFT space historically, mainly because of the trustless ownership advantages NFTs provide to collectors. Artists certainly tapped into this concept, particularly around “tokenness”.

Ownership-based Runtime Art takes this concept and forms aesthetics through it. Since smart contracts can access collectors' balances of different coins as well as other NFTs, we can build art around this information. Artists can even offer unique on-chain traits to their collectors based on ownership of their prior work; which would go away if the work is transferred away.” (Chainleft, 2024)

Appendix 3 - Mouse Interaction Analysis with ChatGPT

examine this image, and tell me if you think this represents an interactive interface.

Yes, this image appears to represent an interactive interface, likely for a simple game or application called "Jumpy Dot." The presence of the word "START" suggests that this is a clickable button to begin the game or activity. The score indicator at the bottom (0/0) further implies that this interface keeps track of a score or progress, which is common in interactive applications.

The overall layout and text suggest that this is likely the start or main menu screen of the game or application. The minimalist design and centered text are also typical of simple or casual games.

if I were to click on the image to interact with it, give me approximate x,y coordinates where I should click

To interact with the "START" button on this interface, you should aim to click near the center of the screen where the "START" text is located.

Given that the image is square, with a resolution of 511x511 pixels, an approximate location would be:

- **x-coordinate:** Around 255 (close to the center horizontally)
- **y-coordinate:** Around 350 (slightly below the center vertically, as the "START" text is lower on the screen)

So, an approximate coordinate to click would be **(255, 350)**. This should be close to the "START" button and trigger the interaction.

Figure 7.3: ChatGPT analysis of interaction

Appendix 4 - Evaluation Form

ARKIVO.ART evaluation form

Your name (optional):

Twitter handle:

Please access **arkivo.art** on a desktop web browser
Spend a minute or two getting acquainted with the interface

Section 1 – First impressions

Q1: What are your first impressions of the system?

Section 2 – Networked OBJKTs

Do you know any OBJKTs which make network requests? yes no

If yes, please use the search facility to find it.

If not, please jump to Section 3

Q2: What is the OBJKT? (please specify title/author):

Q3: Were you able to find the OBJKT? yes no

Q4: Is the OBJKT properly classified as networked? yes no

Section 3 – Non-Networked OBJKTs

Do you know any code-based OBJKTs which **do not** make network requests? yes no

If yes, please use the search facility to find it.

If not, please jump to Section 4

Q5: What is the OBJKT? (please specify title/author):

Q6: Were you able to find the OBJKT? yes no

Q7: Is the OBJKT properly classified as non-networked? yes no

Section 4 – General Feedback

Q8: Please specify any difficulties that you experienced using the platform

Q9: What feature(s) would you like to see implemented in this platform?

Q10: Do you have any other suggestions for improvements?

Please return the completed form via one of the following channels:

Twitter/X: [@ktorn](#)

Discord: @ktorn

Email: daniel.farinha@usj.edu.mo

